

Multilevel management of irregular migration and return in Austria: new insights and data

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List of abbreviations/acronyms

AMDC.....	<i>Austrian Micro Data Centre</i>
AuslBG.....	<i>Ausländerbeschäftigungsgesetz / Foreign Workers Employment Act</i>
BBU.....	<i>Bundesagentur für Versorgungs- und Unterstützungsleistungen / Federal Agency for Reception and Support Services with limited Liability</i>
BFA.....	<i>Bundesamt für Fremdenwesen und Asyl / Federal Office for Asylum and Immigration</i>
BK.....	<i>Bundeskriminalamt / Federal Criminal Police Office</i>
BMI.....	<i>Bundesministerium für Inneres / Ministry of Interior</i>
BvWG.....	<i>Bundesverwaltungsgericht / Federal Administrative Court</i>
ECHR.....	<i>European Convention on Human Rights</i>
EES.....	<i>Entry / Exit System</i>
ETIAS.....	<i>European Travel Information and Authorization System</i>
EURA.....	<i>EU Readmission Agreement</i>
FPG.....	<i>Fremdenpolizeigesetz / Aliens Police Act</i>
FPÖ.....	<i>Freiheitliche Partei Österreichs / Freedom Party Austria</i>
FSW.....	<i>Fonds Soziales Wien / Vienna Social Fund</i>
IFA.....	<i>Integrierte Fremdenadministration / the System of integrated Foreign Administration</i>
IOM.....	<i>International Organization for Migration</i>
JCP.....	<i>Joint Coordination Platform</i>
JOO.....	<i>Joint Operational Office</i>
NAG.....	<i>Niederlassungs- und Aufenthaltsgesetz / Settlement and Residence Act</i>
OTL.....	<i>Order to leave</i>
ÖVP.....	<i>Die Volkspartei Österreichs / Austrian People's Party</i>
POPREG.....	<i>Population Register</i>
RR.....	<i>Return Rate</i>
TCN.....	<i>Third-country national</i>
UNHCR.....	<i>United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees</i>
URESPOP.....	<i>usually resident population</i>
Vfgh.....	<i>Verfassungsgericht / Constitutional Court</i>
VIS.....	<i>Visa Information System</i>
VMÖ.....	<i>Verein Menschenrechte Österreich / Human Rights Association Austria</i>

Key findings

- Austria has long prioritised return over other responses to the presence of irregular migrants, albeit the scope for alternatives to return has been expanded with the reform of humanitarian stay and the related introduction of a toleration status (“Duldung”, in 2009). Nevertheless, regularisation options are used sparingly.
- In 2015 (‘refugee crisis’) and 2022, the number of asylum applications in Austria peaked significantly, followed by a sharp drop in the following years. The ‘refugee crisis’ (2015/2016) was a decisive factor in the implementation of a series of changes to the legal framework aiming to strengthen migration control, to prevent irregular migration and to increase the number of returns. These priorities remain highly relevant in the Austrian context. After 2022, Austria has initiated and implemented various cooperations linked to readmission with relevant countries of origin.
- In relation to conditions of third-country nationals pending return, the Basic Care system (“Grundversorgung”), in place since 2004 is the main relevant framework, giving the provinces an important role in providing support, including housing to persons in return procedures.
- Most provinces do not have additional policies targeting persons pending return or other irregular migrants, although some policies exist, e.g. in Vienna, addressing emergency housing or health needs.
- The past decade or so has seen significant legal reforms in the area of return and in particular a major institutional re-organisation, with the establishment of the Federal Agency for Migration and Asylum in 2013 (“Bundesamt für Fremdenwesen und Asyl”, BFA, operational as of 2014) and the Federal Agency for Federal Care (“Bundesbetreuungsgentur”, BBU) in 2019 (operational as of 2020).
- The role of civil society organisations in return has been diminished with the shift of certain responsibilities, notably regarding return counselling to the BBU.
- The high courts, and in particular the Constitutional Court has had a key role in shaping and adjusting the relevant legal framework.
- Cooperation with third-countries is a strong priority in regard to return in Austria and Austria has concluded several agreements since the migration and refugee crisis 2015.
- There is a shift, on the one hand to more informal agreements with third countries, and on the other, to broader migration agreements, including also other areas than return.
- Available estimates suggest that by and large there has not been a great increase of the irregular migrant resident population in Austria. This said, irregular inflows have been volatile, leading to a large workload and important bottlenecks in managing both asylum and return procedures.
- Yet available data also suggest a significant scale of onward migration and therefore a significant number of inactive, “cold” cases.

SECTION 1: Management of irregular migration and return at national and sub-national level

The legislative framework and practices to manage irregularly staying third – country nationals and return

In Austria, the Asylum Act (“Asylgesetz”), the Aliens’ Police Act (FPG– ‘Fremdenpolizeigesetz’), the Settlement and Residence Act (NAG – ‘Niederlassungs- und Aufenthaltsgesetz’), as well as the Foreign Workers Employment Act (AuslBG – ‘Ausländerbeschäftigungsgesetz’) provide the legal framework for irregular migration and return (Kratzmann & Reyhani, 2012). The interplay and complexity of the legal framework is reflected, among other things, in the extent of reforms and legal changes (Hinterberger, 2023), partly caused by decisions of the Constitutional Court, which in recent years has repeatedly identified laws as unconstitutional leading to the repeal (partly without replacement) and changes of laws.¹

- The **Asylum Act** provides the legal framework for the asylum procedure and the issuance of *residence permits for exceptional circumstances*² (“Aufenthaltstitel aus berücksichtigungswürdigen Gründen”);
- The **Aliens’ Police Act** regulates, among other things, the issuance of measures terminating residence in the case of third-country nationals who stay in Austria irregularly³, and the issuance of visas (Hinterberger, 2023; Kratzmann & Reyhani, 2012);
- The **Settlement and Residence Act** (NAG), also an instrument of immigration control, defines the right of settlement and residence (Hinterberger, 2023; Kratzmann & Reyhani, 2012);
- The **Foreign Workers Employment Act** and the corresponding provisions under residence law in the Settlement and Residence Act and the Aliens’ Police Act constitute the legal basis for the admission of foreign workers to the Austrian labour market (Kratzmann & Reyhani, 2012; Ministry of Labour and Economy, 2023).⁴

In the following, the content of the various legislative changes directly related to irregular migration and return are described. The legal reforms, that provide the basis for changes at institutional level and the associated areas of responsibility in the field of irregular migration and return, are explained in the subsequent section.

¹ More than half of individual complaints assessed by the Constitutional Courts concerned the area of asylum (and related field) (Verfassungsgerichtshof, 2023).

² There are only limited options for regularisation in Austria, namely the different residence permits issued for exceptional circumstances. The regularisation mechanisms in Austria can be described as a two-stage procedure: In the first stage, a temporary residence status or a toleration is granted, in the second stage it is possible to obtain a regular legal status (Kraler, 2009). More detailed information can be found in the subsection *Pathways out of irregularity: Formal Regularisation*.

³ § 52 of the Aliens’ Police Act, which deals with the issuance of return decisions, transposes Article 6 of the EU Return Directive (Directive 2008/115/EC), Article 6 stipulates that third-country nationals who do not have a right of residence should either be issued a residence permit or a return decision (Lutz & Mananashvili, 2016).

⁴ Table 3 (Overview of relevant legislative changes between 2009 and 2022) in the ANNEX provides an overview of significant legal changes in this time period. The year 2009 was included due to the high importance with regard to the development and current status of residence permits for exceptional circumstances (“Aufenthaltstitel aus berücksichtigungswürdigen Gründen”) and toleration (“Duldung”).

Reforms of the legislative framework related to irregular migration and return

The '**Bleiberechtsnovelle**' (*Amendment to the "right to remain"*) of **2009** has been major legislative landmark in relation to clarifying and expanding **possibilities of regularisation** of irregularly resident migrants in Austria. It included the introduction of the *special protection residence permit* ("Aufenthaltsberechtigung besonderer Schutz")⁵ and of the *residence permit in particularly exceptional cases* ("Aufenthaltsberechtigung in besonders berücksichtigungswürdigen Fällen")⁶. This regulation addressed persons who have already been in an overlong asylum procedure, which was finally decided negatively, and who could not qualify for a *residence permit for reasons of Art 8 ECHR*. Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), which guarantees the right to respect for private and family life regardless of the legal status of persons (Hinterberger, 2023). The reform of the humanitarian residence for foreigners is a consequence of a judgement of the Constitutional Court which found that the previous regulation that residence permits for humanitarian reasons could only be granted ex officio without a right to application be unconstitutional (Constitutional Court, 2008). The right of application was one essential adjustment of this reform (Hinterberger, 2023).

In the early 1990s, the possibility of postponement of enforced return due to legal and factual barriers was enshrined in the Austrian Aliens Act. This step was intended to provide people who could not be deported for legal or factual reasons with legal certainty until the return decision was re-evaluated. In the **Aliens Amendment Act** ("Fremdenrechtsänderungsgesetz") **2009** the legal status of 'toleration' was created and legally enshrined in the Aliens Police Act § 46a. Toleration can be granted on the basis of three legal grounds, which are in line with EU law obligations⁷:

(1) the principle of non-refoulement.

(2) in cases in which international protection is withdrawn (e.g. due to commitment of a serious crime) and return is not possible, e.g. because of the situation in the country of origin.

(3) in the case of a violation of the right to respect for private and family life. Here, too, there is a link to the ECHR (Art. 8(2) of the ECHR) (Hinterberger & Klammer, 2020).

Another reform of toleration took place within the **Aliens Amendment Act 2015**. This amendment also affects the procedure for issuing a return decision and stipulate that when issuing a return decision, the admissibility of the return decision must be examined with regard to a possible refoulement violation by the Federal Office for Asylum and Immigration (BFA – 'Bundesamt für Fremdenwesen und Asyl') (Hinterberger, 2023).

Changes of the legislative framework after 2015, in particular in 2016 and 2017, must also be seen in the context of the so-called 'refugee crisis' and a change in social and political discourse from a 'welcoming culture' to an increasing negative attitude towards refugees (Gruber, 2017; Rheindorf & Wodak, 2018; Thiele et al., 2021). Policy measures and changes of the legal framework aimed at strengthening migration control, the prevention of irregular migration and the (forced or voluntary) return of irregular migrants and rejected asylum seekers (Ataç & Schütze, 2020; Homberger, Kirchhoff, Mallet-Garcia, et al., 2022, p. 6; Wodak, 2018).

⁵ Prerequisites for application were among others, that the suspension of enforcement was granted more than once for at least one year (Hinterberger 2023).

⁶ As part of the reform, the residence permits for exceptional circumstances were transferred from the Settlement and Residence Act (NAG) back to the Aliens Police Law ("Fremdenpolizeigesetz", FPG).

⁷ The non-refoulement principle and the right to respect family and private life, Art 8 of the ECHR.

The **amendment of the Asylum Act 2016** introduced further specifications on regulations on the counselling of asylum seekers, which was at this point of time mainly under the responsibility of national NGOs (*Diakonie* and *ARGE Rechtsberatung* and *Verein Menschenrechte Österreich (VMÖ)*). Furthermore, the so called “Asyl auf Zeit” (temporary asylum) was implemented, meaning that persons who have applied for asylum after November 2015 don’t receive a permanent (temporarily not limited) settlement rights in the case of a positive decision on their application, but the validity of the status is limited to three years and then is assessed again and might be withdrawn or renewed and transferred into a permanent stay (Biffli, 2017). In addition, a waiting period of three years has been set for holders of subsidiary protection status before they can apply for family reunification (Amendment of the Asylum Procedures Act, 2016).

Changes by the **Aliens Law Amendment Act 2017** included various measures to prevent migrants who received a return decision from absconding intended to support the enforcement of the obligation to leave the country (Stiller & Humer, 2020), such as mandatory return counselling, area restrictions, residence obligations, a time extension of the period of possible detention⁸ and administrative penalties. The amendment foresees the following measures:

1. A *Residence obligation* is ordered by means of an administrative decision and entails that the person *has to stay* in a designated federal accommodation facility until leaving the country. In any case, accommodation, food and medical care are provided. The residence obligation can be enforced, if third-country nationals who received a legally valid return decision and are not tolerated in different case constellations, such as
 - no period for voluntary departure was granted⁹; or
 - after expiry of the period for voluntary departure, certain facts justify the assumption that the third-country national will not comply with his or her obligation to leave the country¹⁰;
 - certain facts justify the assumption that the third-country national will not comply with the departure (Aliens Law Amendment Act § 57)¹¹.

⁸ Before the changes 2017, detention pending deportation was limited to 10 months within 18 months. The “regular” maximum detention period for juveniles is 2 months. The “regular” maximum detention period for adults is 4 months. The “regular” maximum detention period for young adults was 2 months. The “regular” maximum detention period for adults was 4 months. The regulation from 2017 stipulates that detention pending deportation can generally be maintained for up to 18 months. The “regular” maximum detention period for young adults was extended to 3 months, and for adults to 6 months.

⁹ The period for voluntary return is set together with a return decision and is defined in §55 of the Aliens Police Act (2005): No period for voluntary return might be granted, if (1) the suspensive effect of an appeal is withdrawn according §18 of the BFA – Procedural Act (BFA - Procedural Act, 2014), (2) for cases of a rejecting decision pursuant to § 68 AVG, Section 2: Other amendments to decisions - Amendment and revocation ex officio (General Administrative Procedure Act, 1991).

¹⁰ Facts to be considered: if he/she has not taken part in a return counseling interview; has changed his/her place of residence or place of usual residence after the deadline for voluntary departure has expired and has not informed the Federal Office of this; has not cooperated in the actions necessary to obtain a permit or travel document; has declared during the asylum procedure, the procedure for issuing the return decision or the return counseling interview that he/she does not wish to comply with his/her obligation to leave the country; has deceived or attempted to deceive about his/her country of origin or identity during the asylum procedure or the procedure for issuing the return decision.

¹¹ The assessment has to take into account that the third-country national has already failed to comply with an order to leave the country; the transfer period had to be extended for reasons for which person concerned is responsible; the third-country national re-entered the federal territory while an order to leave the country was in force; or the third-country national deceived or attempted to deceive about his identity, his country of origin or his travel route during the asylum procedure (Aliens Law Amendment Act § 57).

2. *Area restrictions* are implemented, if foreigners against whom an enforceable return decision has been issued, are obliged to take up residence in a federal accommodation facility (see residence obligation) until departure. In this case, the persons have to remain in the area of the district administrative authority in which the federal accommodation facility is located. Foreigners concerned have to be informed about the area restrictions, the boundaries of the area and consequences of failing to comply with the area restriction (Aliens Law Amendment Act § 52a). Area restrictions and related obligations of the third-country national are suspended if and for as long as (1) the return decision is temporarily unenforceable; (2) his or her stay in Austria is tolerated, or (3) he or she is deprived of his or her personal liberty (Aliens Law Amendment Act § 52a).

Third-country nationals (TCNs) who have received an enforceable return decision, but do not comply to leave the country within the mandatory time, commit an *administrative offence*. The administrative penalties that were first introduced in 2017 are currently between 100 and 1000€ in case of non-compliance. In case of non-legal residence penalties of up to 15,000€ or imprisonment up to six weeks can be imposed (Aliens Police Act §120).^{12 13}

The **Basic Act on Social Assistance** (“Sozialhilfe-Grundsatzgesetz”) **2019** (Basic Act on Social Assistance, 2019) sets a national framework for the regulation of non-contributory social benefits and should replace the previous needs-based minimum income system by social assistance. The details are regulated by provincial legislation. Provinces are also responsible for its implementation. In addition to setting a binding framework that the provinces must adhere to when implementing this framework law, the act also contains a number optional provisions that give the provinces a range of options when drafting their new laws (*Allgemeines Zur Sozialhilfe/Mindestsicherung*, 2023). Several provinces have had concerns, which is reflected by its patchy implementation: As of January 1, 2024 six out of nine provinces (Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Salzburg, Styria, Carinthia and Vorarlberg) have adopted the Basic Act on Social Assistance (*Allgemeines Zur Sozialhilfe/Mindestsicherung*, 2023). Other provinces have implemented the Basic Act on Social Assistance in part or not at all; in these cases, the minimum income system (or parts thereof) remain in force.¹⁴ This legal reform was criticized by NGOs, UNHCR as well as by various provinces. Among the points of criticism, it was particularly emphasized that there are potentially long intervals between a return decision and the actual return or a decision for toleration or a residence permit for exceptional circumstances (Rosenberger et al., 2018; Stiller & Humer, 2020). In addition, there have been repeated changes in recent years, triggered by rulings by the Constitutional Court (Vfgh – ‘Verfassungsgericht’), that declared the maximum rates for children and the linking of language skills to social assistance (2022) as well as compulsory benefits in kind (2023) to be unconstitutional (*Allgemeines Zur Sozialhilfe/Mindestsicherung*, 2023; Basic Act on Social Assistance, 2019)

In principle, the Basic Act on Social Assistance for third-country nationals must be seen in conjunction with basic care for foreigners in need of assistance and protection (“Grundversorgung für hilfs- und

¹² Non-legal residence is also a possible outcome of situations other than non-compliance with a return decision, for if a third-country national overstays an expired student visa. In this case, the third-country-national can extend or apply for a new visa under certain circumstances, and no OTL is issued at all as it is only a missed administrative step.

¹³ Table 4: Overview of the most relevant categories of migrants in an irregular situation in Austria and possible implications, such as administrative penalties, entry bans and deportation) in the ANNEX provides an overview of the most relevant categories of migrants in an irregular situation in Austria and possible implications, such as administrative penalties, entry bans and deportation.

¹⁴ Third-country nationals are subject to the following key points regarding eligibility: Third-country nationals are generally only entitled to social assistance or minimum benefits if they have already lived legally in Austria for more than five years. Persons entitled to asylum are entitled to social assistance or minimum benefits from the time they are granted refugee status. Asylum seekers are not entitled to social assistance or minimum benefits. Persons entitled to subsidiary protection are only entitled to core social assistance benefits that do not exceed the level of basic care (“Grundversorgung”).

schutzbedürftige Fremde”; 2005). Persons in need of assistance are foreign nationals who are unable or not sufficiently able to secure the basic necessities of life for themselves and their dependants living in the same household. Persons in need of protection are asylum seekers, as well as persons whose asylum application has been approved and who can still receive basic welfare support for up to four months after being granted asylum; foreigners without the right of residence who cannot be deported for legal or factual reasons, with or without a negative asylum decision; foreigners who are waiting to be returned abroad (Basic Care Act, 2005). Basic care includes a small amount of cash and is tailored to the aforementioned groups and includes various services¹⁵. Here, too, there is a division of responsibilities between the federal government and the provinces in the form of the basic care agreement, whereby the legal framework is federal law and the Federal Agency for Reception and Support Services with limited Liability (BBU) is responsible for processing at federal level (see next subsection). The federal government runs accommodation facilities (initial reception centres for asylum seekers) and is responsible for the reception of asylum seekers. Furthermore, the federal government is responsible for the allocation of asylum seekers to the provinces, taking into account the allocation key; the transport to the initial reception centres and from the initial reception centres to the accommodation facilities of the provinces; all kind of registrations necessary for health insurance; the administrative and financial processing; if necessary and at the request of the provinces, support in the redistribution of foreigners to other provinces and the coordination and implementation of measures concerning return programs. The federal government informs the provinces about decisions relevant to the asylum procedure and is responsible for precautionary capacities in the event of accommodation bottlenecks in the provinces. The tasks of the provinces are to care for the asylum seekers assigned by the Coordination Office, to decide on the admission of foreigners to the provincial accommodation facilities, or also to decide on the release of foreigners from those (in the case of asylum seekers the BFA must be involved); to create and maintain the necessary infrastructure; to register with the health insurance; to provide current data on the utilization of capacities; to support the BFA in conducting asylum procedures (e.g. by delivering summonses and decisions to the asylum seeker); to process the necessary personal data of asylum seekers to carry out return actions; to report asylum seekers who are subject to the asylum procedure to the BFA (Basic Care Agreement, 2004).

The **Basic Act on Social Assistance** (“Sozialhilfe-Grundsatzgesetz”), the Basic Care Act (2005) and the Basic Care Agreement (2004) highlight the importance of cooperation between the federal government and the provinces in the field of asylum and return management. Even if federal law takes precedence, the federal government is dependent on functioning cooperation with the provinces for implementation processes, data and information sharing. The implementation of the Basic Act on Social Assistance, which has now been ongoing for years, also demonstrates that the provinces are making use of the leeway and also await changes to the legal framework: rulings by the Constitutional Court declared the maximum rates for children and the linking of language skills to social assistance (2022) as well as compulsory benefits in kind (2023) to be unconstitutional (*Allgemeines Zur Sozialhilfe/Mindestsicherung*, 2023; Basic Act on Social Assistance, 2019) - points that were criticized by some provinces in advance.

Changes in the institutional framework

In terms of relevant institutional changes since 2010 in the field of irregular migration and return management, the **Aliens Authority Restructuring Acts in 2012** and **Amendment Acts in 2013 and 2014**, as

¹⁵ Included services are accommodation in suitable accommodation; the provision of food, a monthly allowance for persons in organized accommodation and for unaccompanied minors; the guarantee of medical care and the provision of health care; information, advice and social support; transport costs for transfers and official charges, as well as the costs incurred for school attendance; measures to structure the daily routine in case of need; benefits in kind or in cash to obtain clothing; costs of a funeral or a repatriation amount; return counselling; travel costs and a one-off bridging allowance in the event of voluntary return to the country of origin in special cases (Basic Care Agreement, 2004).

well as the **BBU Establishment Act** (“Bundesagentur für Betreuung- und Unterstützungsleistungen” (BBU) - Federal Agency for Reception and Support Services with limited Liability) **2019** were of particular importance.

The **Aliens Authority Restructuring Acts** (2012)¹⁶ (“Fremdenbehördenneustrukturierungsgesetz”) and the **Amendment Acts in 2013 and 2014** provide the legal framework (BFA-Establishment Act [“BFA-Einrichtungsgesetz”), BFA-Procedural Act [“BFA-Verfahrensgesetz”]) for the establishment of the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA), which began operating in January, 2014. With the **Aliens’ Authorities Restructuring Act 2014** the provision on *Residence permits for exceptional circumstances* (Asylum Act § 54) was transferred from the Settlement and Residence Act to the 7th main section of the Asylum Act and newly regulated (Asylum Act; BFA - Procedural Act, 2014; Hinterberger, 2023). This transfer also reflects the regulation of the areas of responsibility set out in the BFA Procedural Act. As illustrated in the visualisation of the return process (Figure 1, below), corresponds to the possibilities of implementing *residence permits for exceptional circumstances* as a regularisation option (for more comprehensive explanations, see the subsections “Return decisions: Competent authorities and areas of responsibility” and “Pathways out of irregularity: Formal Regularisation”).

The BFA is directly subordinate to the Ministry of the Interior. The headquarter (directorate) is in Vienna, furthermore regional directorates are situated in each of the nine provinces of Austria. Other organisational units are the Initial reception centres (“Erstaufnahmestellen” [EAST]) East and West, the EAST Airport and also field offices of the regional directorates. Its main tasks include conducting first-instance asylum and alien law proceedings (excluding criminal proceedings and visa matters) and issuing *residence permits for exceptional circumstances*.

The **BBU Establishment Act 2019** (BBU-Errichtungsgesetz, BBU-G 2019) marks fundamental changes in the organisation and practical implementation of the migration, asylum and return management. According §2 of the Act, the ‘Federal Agency for Reception and Support Services Ltd’ (“Bundesbetreuungsgesellschaft”, BBU), has the legal mandate for

- the provision of care according the **Agreement between the Federal Government and the Provinces** on Joint Measures for Temporary Basic Provision for Foreigners in Need of Assistance and Protection (asylum seekers, persons entitled to asylum, displaced persons and other persons who cannot be deported for legal or factual reasons) in Austria, insofar as this is the responsibility of the Federal Government,
- the provision of legal counsel before the Federal Office, and the Federal Administrative Court,
- the implementation of return counselling and return assistance,
- the provision of human rights observers for the purpose of systematic monitoring of deportations,
- the provision of interpreters and translators before the authorities and the Federal Administrative Court.

The BBU reports to the BFA and started its activities in 2020/2021, during the COVID-19 pandemic, which complicated the provision of different services, such as legal and return counseling. The concentration of these different services under one entity subordinate to the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA) has been initiated under Centre-Right coalition government between the Austrian People’s Party (ÖVP) and the right-wing Freedom Party (FPÖ), with the explicit intention to increase the control of the state over return procedures and reduce the role of non-governmental organisations in return policy (Schweitzer, 2022). The establishment of the BBU was criticized by different NGOs and UNHCR right from the beginning. In the course of establishing the BBU, contracts with external providers of legal advice, the NGOs *Diakonie* and *ARGE Rechtsberatung* and *Verein Menschenrechte Österreich* (VMÖ), were terminated (Gahleitner-Gertz, 2020). Concerns were partly related to this, including the structural dependence of the

¹⁶ Fremdenbehördenneustrukturierungsgesetz 2012: BFA-Verfahrensgesetz - BFA-VG StF: BGBl. I No. 87/2012 (NR: GP XXIV RV 1803 AB 1889 p. 166. BR: AB 8774 p. 812.):

https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2012_I_87/BGBLA_2012_I_87.pdf#sig

BBU, possible changes in access and target group orientation and a decoupling of support and counselling services from NGOs (Asylkoordination, 2020; Fritsche et al., 2019). A further change of the legal framework concerns the provision of legal assistance for first-instance proceedings. In order for people to exercise their right to free legal advice, they must make an appointment with the responsible unit of the BBU within 72 hours (three days) after the BFA informed them the application for international protection will be denied. If this deadline is not met, free legal advice will only be provided, depending on the available resources of the BBU (Art 49(1) BFA-VG). In addition, travel costs incurred are not reimbursed, which represents a further possible hurdle to access to legal advice (Gahleitner-Gertz, 2022). The standardization and clearly defined quality requirements of obligatory qualifications of legal advisors and thus the assurance of legal advice are mainly received positively in reports and experts' statements (Ebner, 2022; EMN Austria, 2021; Gahleitner-Gertz, 2022). To ensure systematic standardization, IOM was commissioned, with support from the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, to create guidelines on which return counselling and the subject area could be further developed. These guidelines from IOM are sorted thematically and generally describe the voluntary return landscape in Austria, the historical development, and the status quo in 2021, as well as the integration landscape, the content of a return counselling interview and the special handling of vulnerable persons. Since then, there have been further developments in the following years, which BBU has actively promoted, such as in the form of a separate focus team dedicated to the topic of training and further education, which is developing a training catalogue for new return counsellors, as well as further training measures for all return counsellors. These measures cover the entire area of social skills, multicultural competence in the direction of language skills, as well as basic asylum and alien law issues (Expert interview 05 on the **process** leading to and following a **return decision** with a representative of Department Return, Reintegration and Quality Development of the Federal Ministry of the Interior, March 2024).

In 2022, the Austrian Constitutional Court examined the conformity of the BBU legal advice system with constitutional and fundamental rights requirements. In a preliminary decision from December 2022, the Constitutional Court noted various concerns, relating to independence and accountability of the agency, the lack of clear guarantee of the right to a fair trial, and an insufficient guarantee of a minimum level of de facto effectiveness for those seeking legal protection, thus raising issues relating to the rule of law and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. (Reyhani, 2023; Verfassungsgerichtshof E 3608/2021-28 Ua.*, 2022).

In the preliminary ruling, the Constitutional Court also announced to examine whether the statutory provisions on independence, freedom from instructions and confidentiality are sufficient to prevent conflicts of interest (Reyhani, 2023; Verfassungsgerichtshof E 3608/2021-28 Ua.*, 2022). In December 2023 the Constitutional Court ruled that the legal form of BBU GmbH is constitutional. However, the independence of the BBU from the BFA in providing legal advice to asylum seekers and foreigners is only contractually guaranteed, but not sufficiently guaranteed by law. This violates the right to an effective legal remedy. The corresponding legal provisions in the BBU Establishment Act (BBU-G) and the BFA Procedures Act (BFA-VG) have therefore been repealed as unconstitutional, with the legislator given a deadline until July 1, 2025 to enact new legislation (*Vfgh Beschluss*, 2023).

Challenges and peculiarities on sub-national levels: the capital Vienna and the province of Burgenland

In the context of relevant governmental authorities responsible for irregular migration and return, inter-governmental cooperation between the different levels (the federal level and the provinces) is substantial. The reception of asylum seekers is regulated by federal law, it is relevant for the handling of foreigners with a toleration status or of migrants who have received a return decision and are in the process of return preparation (*Basic Care Agreement*, 2004 and the *Basic Act on Social Assistance*, 2019). Although the provinces' scope of action is thus determined by federal legislation, there are various possibilities, e.g.

through making use of legal leeway, or the cooperation and funding of NGOs. In the following, the capital of Austria, Vienna, as well as the province of Burgenland will be discussed as examples of how the province-specific situation with regard to irregular migration and the irregular resident population is dealt with and which strategies and measures are implemented. The example of Vienna was chosen because of the extensive cooperations and funding activities with NGOs, which allow that irregularly resident migrants are at least not excluded from essential services. Also, Vienna's share of asylum seekers and rejected asylum seekers is larger than of any other province. The province of Burgenland, on the other hand, is discussed due to its special geographical features, namely the almost 400 km long shared border with Hungary and further smaller border areas with Slovenia and Slovakia.

The province Burgenland

Burgenland is the province in Austria with by far the highest number of apprehensions of migrants crossing the borders irregularly both smuggled and independently moving migrants. In 2022, there was an overall increase of over 150% in the number of total apprehensions includes apprehensions of persons who entered and stayed irregularly, smugglers and smuggled persons. Most of the detected border crossings to Austria were from Hungary (68,767 persons, 63%), Italy (4,941 persons, 4%) and Slovakia (2,875 persons, 2%). In 2022, 71,411 persons were apprehended in the province of Burgenland, followed by Vienna with 11,148 apprehensions, Lower Austria (bordering Slovakia and Czechia) with 9,849 apprehensions and Tyrol (bordering Italy, Germany and Switzerland) with 5,581 apprehensions (BMI, 2023). In terms of apprehensions at district level, the Burgenland districts of Neusiedl am See (38,838 apprehensions) and Oberpullendorf (25,898) are well ahead of districts in other provinces, while the third and fourth-ranked districts of Bruck an der Leitha (in Lower Austria) and Vienna Favoriten had comparatively few apprehensions (Bruck an der Leitha: 4,423; Vienna Favoriten: 4,178) (BMI, 2023). Due to this the Burgenland border has been and still is in the focus of numerous measures of border control and against smuggling and trafficking in human beings. At federal level, these circumstances were addressed in 2021 with structural adjustments to the Federal Criminal Police Office to pool expertise and clearly define responsibilities. Since December 2021, the new Department 8 *Smuggling, Trafficking in Human Beings and Special Investigations* has been operational at the Federal Criminal Police Office. It has a team of around 50 experts and investigates smuggling, human trafficking, and offenses such as visa fraud, benefit fraud and illegal gambling. Another key player is the Joint Operational Office (JOO) with a focus on international cooperation and the Balkan route and countries located there (BMI, 2023). Regarding the significance of the shared border with Hungary, Minister of the Interior Karner has repeatedly emphasized the importance of cooperation with Hungary in recent years and has reinforced this in talks with Hungarian Interior Minister Sándor Pintér. The Austrian police supports the Hungarian police with mixed patrols on Hungarian territory and also in the protection of the external border with Serbia, and further priority actions are planned in the border area (Ministry of Interior & Federal Criminal Police Office, n.d.-b).

The capital and province Vienna

The importance of the province and the capital Vienna results from a combination of several factors: on the one hand, Vienna has a very diverse population, which is also reflected in the organisation and external presentation of many of the city's central service institutions; on the other hand, all ministries and various migration and integration-related institutions that are assigned to the ministries (for example the Austrian Integration Fund (ÖIF) or the BBU) are located in Vienna or at least have their headquarters in the capital. In addition, there is a very high density of NGOs in Vienna, which are also easy to reach thanks to the extensive infrastructure. Also, relevant international organisations (such as the International Organization for Migration (IOM) or the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)) are located here. The infrastructure and mobility options, and thus the accessibility of relevant facilities, is a factor that should not be underestimated, especially in rural areas of Austria, and can be an obstacle to accessing service facilities.

Irregular migrants in Austria have hardly any access to service facilities or often avoid them for fear that their irregular status could be revealed. Service centres that offer anonymous support services or whose services can be used regardless of residence status are therefore of particular importance. Organisations offering such service soften have several funding sources; in Vienna, funding from the Vienna Social Fund (FSW – ‘Fonds Soziales Wien’, an agency under private law) is of particular importance. Organisations, which do not address irregular migrants specifically, but are accessible independently from the residence status, are e.g., AmberMed (Diakonie Flüchtlingsdienst gem. GmbH, n.d.) providing health care services for persons without health insurance, and the Neunerhaus (*Neunerhaus*, n.d.) (healthcare, homelessness), among others.

Also noteworthy is the City of Vienna's integration concept and related measures, such as the programs *integration from day 1*, funding German courses for migrants in asylum procedure; *StartWien*: multilingual information modules on topics such as housing and the labour market; and a wide range of different integration support services (Expert interview 02, 06/2023; Homberger, Kirchhoff, Mallet, et al., 2022). In addition, the city supports initiatives against trafficking in human beings (Expert interview 02, 06/2023). The City of Vienna has also declared itself a Human Rights City and set up its own Human Rights Office, which is dedicated to the topic as a cross-cutting issue meaning that the city government follows a prioritisation of human rights-oriented policies at the local level (Expert interview 02, 06/2023; Expert interview 03, 06/2023). The City of Vienna has also distinguished itself through its handling and implementation of the Basic Care Agreement, taking in more beneficiaries of basic welfare support under the Basic Care agreement than would be its share. In a similar vein, it has so far only implemented parts of the Basic Act on Social Assistance and provides social assistance more generously than foreseen by the Law (Expert interview 03, 06/2023).

Return decisions: Competent authorities¹⁷ and areas of responsibility

In Austria processes and measures related to irregular migration and return are mainly centralized on federal level, managed by the Ministry of Interior (BMI) and diverse sub-units, such as the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA). The **flow chart** describing the **process** leading to and following a **return decision** is based on the legal framework and the responsibilities of competent authorities in the different stages of the process. Furthermore, pathways into irregularity (e.g. absconding, loss of protection status, rejection of an application for international protection or another residence title, overstaying, irregular entries etc.) and (legal) pathways out of irregularity, such as toleration and regularisation, are included.

The **Ministry of Interior** is responsible, among other things, for security, state borders, the organisation of the service operations of the Federal Police, citizenship, and disaster management, for organizing and conducting elections, referendums, and referendum petitions, and it organizes internal administration in the provinces (“Bundesländer”). The subordinate **Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum** (BFA) has - related to irregular migration and return - the main tasks of conducting first-instance asylum and alien law proceedings - with the exception of criminal proceedings and visa matters - as well as issuing residence permits for exceptional circumstances and toleration cards (Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum, n.d.-c). In the process of the issuance of a return decision, the BFA has to review any possible violations of the non-refoulement principle to identify legal obstacles to return. Legal obstacles include the non-refoulement requirement according to Art. 2 and 3 of the ECHR, which corresponds to §57 of the Asylum Act 2005, which states that a third-country national who is not legally resident in the federal territory, but has been the victim of violence, or needs protection against further violence, a *residence permit for special protection* ex officio or upon application must be granted. Furthermore, this review comprises the check of

¹⁷ The competent and responsible authorities and related web links are listed in Table 5: Governmental authorities and responsibilities) in the ANNEX.

possible violations of the individual's right to private or family life (Art. 8 para 2 of the ECHR), in such cases §55 of the Asylum Act 2005 states that a residence permit ex officio or upon justified application must be granted if this is necessary to maintain private and family life. If, additionally, the third-country national has fulfilled Module 1 of the Integration Agreement, or is in permitted employment at the time of the decision, the income of which reaches the monthly marginal earnings threshold, a *residence permit plus* may be granted (Asylum Act 2005 § 55, 2022; Asylum Act 2005 § 57, 2022). A more comprehensive explanation of the differences between residence permits and their requirements can be found in the subsection "Pathways out of irregularity: Regularisation". Apart from the ex officio process, the BFA also assesses applications submitted in person (that's possible even if the person is in an irregular residence situation) (Hinterberger, 2023). The BFA is also responsible for examining any practical obstacles that may arise during the preparation and organisation of the return.

The areas of responsibilities of the **Federal Agency for Reception and Support Services** (BBU) comprise basic care, (the mandatory) return counselling and assistance, legal advice and legal representation, human rights monitoring, interpretation and translation services. The BBU is a state agency. In the BMI organisation chart, the BBU is assigned to Directorate General V (Migration and International Affairs)/ Directorate V/B (Integrated Border Management, Foreign Nationals Police, Asylum and Return) (Federal Agency for reception and Support Services, n.d.; Ministry of Interior, 2022).

The **Federal Administrative Court Austria** (BvWG – 'Bundesverwaltungsgericht') decides on appeals against decisions of the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum concerning applications for international protection, Austria's responsibility for conducting the asylum procedure (*Dublin procedure*), granting residence permits for humanitarian reasons, decisions on the termination of the stay of foreigners in Austria, organising their departure, imposing detention pending deportation; as well as on complaints about measures and delays, as well as against the refusal of a visa (Bundesverwaltungsgericht Republik Österreich, n.d.). The first appeal against a return decision has a suspensive effect, any further appeals to the Supreme Administrative or Constitutional Court don't cause a suspension of the return decision¹⁸.

The **Austrian Alien Police** is responsible for 1) preventing the unlawful entry of foreigners, 2) supervising the stay of foreigners in the federal territory, 3) deporting foreigners back and transporting them through, and 4) preventing and stopping criminal acts under federal law. The areas of focus of the alien police in the provinces ("Bundesländer") can vary, e.g. the Aliens Police Department in Vienna is also the coordination centre for air and land deportations, especially charter deportations (Aliens Police Act § 2, n.d.; Ministry of Interior, n.d.-b).

Further competent authorities, which are not directly involved in the issuance and implementation of a return decision, but which are relevant actors in the management and implementation of measures related to irregular migration and return are:

The **Federal Criminal Police Office** (BK – "Bundeskriminalamt") supports all provincial criminal investigation offices and subordinate police departments by providing assistance services, support services and controlling. In the context of irregular migration, particular emphasis should be placed on the fields of combating human trafficking, smuggling and organized crime, as well as international police cooperation (Ministry of Interior & Federal Criminal Police Office, n.d.-a).

The **Joint Coordination Platform** (JCP) started its activities in 2021 and is directly assigned to the Federal Ministry of the Interior. The platform is a joint initiative of Austria and interested EU member states and partners. It operates on a permanent basis. The tasks of the JCP comprehend among others the monitoring

¹⁸ Only one appeal to the Federal Administrative Court (BvWG) is possible further, extraordinary appeals to the Supreme Administrative (VwGH) or Constitutional Court (VfGH) comprise cases of contradictory case law requiring the clarification of substantial legal (constitutional) questions.

and analysis as well as strategy and coordination of activities in the Balkan region and Eastern Mediterranean Route; funding and financing programs; as well as antitrafficking (Ministry of Interior).

Tasks of the **Federal Ministry of Finance/ Finance Police** include, among others, the detection of illegal employment of foreigners and of violations of the provisions of the Wage and Social Dumping Prevention Act; and of social fraud. These tasks are particularly important with regard to irregular migrants in irregular work (Federal Ministry of Finance & Finance Police, n.d.). Under certain conditions, the financial police are authorized to arrest migrants with irregular residence status on behalf of the Aliens Police (Humer & Spiegelfeld, 2020).

Figure 1: *Process illustration: The process leading to and following a return decision*¹⁹

¹⁹ The process illustration and description were developed on basis of the Expert interview 05 on the process leading to and following a return decision with a representative of Department Return, Reintegration and Quality Development of the Federal Ministry of the Interior, March 2024.

The process description illustrates the process leading to and following a return decision. A return decision can be issued on the basis of three circumstances: (1) a negative decision on an application for international protection, (2) a determination of irregular stay; or the (3) withdrawal of an international protection status. If an entry ban is imposed, this is issued at the same time as the return decision. If a decision on an entry ban is made at a later stage, a new return decision will also be issued. In any case, the admissibility of a return decision is assessed based on Art. 2, 3 and 8 of the ECHR. If the review of possible refoulement violations is positive, the person will receive a residence permit for exceptional circumstances ex officio in accordance with paragraph 55 und 57 of the Asylum Act. The competent authority for issuing a return decision, the refoulement review and the granting of a residence permit for exceptional circumstances is the BFA.

An appeal against a return decision can be lodged with the Federal Administrative Court (BVwG); this first appeal generally has a suspensive effect. If this application is decided positively, an international protection title or a residence permit for exceptional circumstances might be granted; or the decision is referred back to the first instance (BFA) for further administrative check. In this process, the Federal Administrative Court may also add an entry ban to a decision by the BFA or change the length of the entry ban. In the case of a negative decision and the enforceability of the return decision, the process follows the main axis of the illustration (next steps are the mandatory return counselling, the procurement of all necessary identity and travel documents (obligation to cooperate) and, under certain circumstances, the use of lenient measures, territorial restriction, residence requirement and detention). Other options are to file an appeal to the Supreme Administrative and/or Constitutional Court, which generally has no suspensive effect, even if a suspension of return is possible on application and the probability of a positive decision seems likely to the court. As before, an international protection status is granted in the case of a positive decision and, in rare cases, a residence permit for exceptional circumstances. As in the appeal proceedings regarding decisions of the BFA before the BVwG, it is also possible in the context of extraordinary appeals that the VwGH or VfGH refer the decisions of the BVwG back to the same instance (BVwG) for a new decision. In particular, if the case is dealt with by the Constitutional Court, there is a constitutional context, which means that the Constitutional Court does not deal with issues relating to justice in individual cases, but with fundamental legal issues of principal importance that concern subjective rights that can be derived from the constitution. For this reason, the granting of a residence permit for exceptional circumstances is rare at this level in particular, while the scope for decision-making is somewhat broader in the Federal Administrative Court (BVwG). In the case of a negative decision, the further process follows the main axis shown.

When the return decision is enforceable, the person concerned is obliged to return counselling as well as cooperation in preparation for departure. Under certain circumstances, lenient measures, a residence requirement, a territorial restriction, or detention pending deportation can be ordered by the BFA (see above).

In the case of mandatory return counselling, a distinction must be made between the asylum context and solely alien law procedures. In the asylum context, the legal force of the return decision is decisive; as soon as this comes into force, people are informed in a written form about the mandatory return counselling²⁰.

In alien law proceedings, it is the enforceability of the decision that is decisive. This means that the suspensive effect of a return decision may be withdrawn at the same time. To be able to enforce the return decision, the Federal Administrative Court must nevertheless decide on the withdrawal of the suspensive effect. As soon

²⁰ Return counselling is also mandatory in the case of a negative outcome of an admission procedure and can be ordered by the BFA by procedural order in accelerated proceedings if a negative decision is expected during an asylum interview. Furthermore, the BBU can request return counselling (e.g. in ongoing appeal proceedings for countries with no probability of granting a protection status such as safe countries of origin according to the Regulation on Countries of Origin). If this is done in writing, return counselling is also mandatory.

as this revocation of the suspensive effect is confirmed, return counselling takes place, i.e. from the moment this return counselling is decisive for a measure under aliens' law, i.e. the authority can take a coercive measure to ensure that return counselling takes place again before this coercive measure is carried out. In these cases, the persons concerned are also informed in writing.

The obligation to cooperate arises directly from the law, and it is also possible to impose certain obligations to cooperate by official notification. These include residence requirements and territorial restrictions. In the context of obtaining a home travel certificate, it is also possible, for example, to set mandatory appointments at embassy representations: on the one hand *ex lege*, on the other hand also by decision of the authority.

It is in any step of the process possible to decide for voluntary return, as stated by the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum “[...] *voluntary return is a top priority, also in implementation of corresponding EU requirements - forced return abroad is only an alternative. For this reason, the federal government has been taking numerous measures in the area of voluntary departure for years to provide comprehensive information about the specific options and to intensively promote and support voluntary return. These measures are carried out with the best possible use of co-financing possibilities through existing EU funding pools of the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF)* (translated by the author, BFA, n.d.). Furthermore, it is possible that an individual application for a residence permit for exceptional circumstances²¹ is decided positively after a return decision was issued. However, it must be considered that the application for a residence permit for exceptional circumstances does not cause a suspension of a return decision, unless the application was made before the return decision. As a corollary, the application does not establish a provisional right of residence (Hinterberger, 2023).

From the moment a return decision becomes enforceable, a deadline for voluntary departure of usually two weeks is set, which comes into force when the return decision becomes enforceable (from the moment the authority can act on the basis of the issued return decision). If persons opt for assisted voluntary return, i.e. receives return counselling via the BBU and communicate that they would like to receive return assistance, return assistance can take place organisationally. In practice, the use of organisational support also means that the persons are given more time if necessary, i.e. as long as the persons are in communication with the BBU or the BFA and are continuously working on obtaining the travel documents, resolving their living circumstances in Austria and preparing for departure, the authorities will wait and this will be accepted as such, even if it takes longer than these two weeks. Once the two weeks have elapsed, the authorities have the option of taking coercive measures. But it only does so if communication with the person breaks off.

An application for assisted voluntary return must be submitted to the BBU and confirmed in writing. The content of this confirmation includes which financial benefits are covered, e.g. whether flight tickets are paid for or there are other financial benefits (up to €900), as well as how long this approval is valid for. The financial benefits depend on the point in time during the procedure at which a person voluntarily leaves the country. Contact with the authorities can be broken off for various reasons, e.g. when persons do not need organisational support and decide to leave the country on their own or in case of absconding, The return counselling service reports this to the authorities after a certain period of time and then the authorities themselves go into a survey process, carry out a residence check and determine whether people can still be contacted or not.

²¹ The residence permit for exceptional circumstances are explained in more detail in the next subsection *Pathways out of irregularity: Formal Regularisation*.

The possible outcomes of the process along the main axis of the illustration comprise

1. a follow-up asylum application, in the case of new circumstances, there will be a new examination by the BFA and, depending on how long-ago previous examinations were carried out, the entire process may be repeated.
2. a new issuance of a return decision and the possible repetition of the entire process due to a new factual situation (again depending on the time gap to a previous inspection by the BFA)
3. The enforcement of the return decision and return to a third-country of country of citizenship.
4. (independent) voluntary return and voluntary assisted return (, both of which are possible at every stage of the procedure. In the case of independent voluntary departure, people comply with the obligation to leave the country on their own initiative, without further contact with the authorities or support services.
5. positive decision on an application for a residence permit under the Settlement and Residence Act (NAG). NAG applications are generally only possible abroad. Only within the scope of Art. 8 of the ECHR can they also be made in Austria.
6. a positive decision on an application for a residence permit for exceptional circumstances.
7. the marriage with an EU citizen who has made use of the right to move and reside freely within the Member States (ex lege beneficiary third-country national).

The BFA re-examines the return decision and the refoulement review, for example, if a person absconds and is apprehended again after a longer time. The further process depends on whether there are indications that the person's personal circumstances have changed, how long it has been since the last return decision, what was stated during the interrogation, whether the circumstances in the country of origin have changed, or whether the person has left and re-entered Austria in the meantime. In these cases, the question of the validity of the return decision arises and then it is an option that a new return decision with the entire related history is necessary.

All these circumstances mean that a mere calculation of the number of return decisions issued for departures is not meaningful when it comes to determining how many people who are obliged to leave the country or are de facto still in the country.

Pathways out of irregularity: Regularisation

There are only limited options for regularisation in Austria, namely the different residence permits issued for exceptional circumstances. The regularisation mechanisms in Austria can be described as a two-stage procedure: In the first stage, a **temporary residence status or a toleration** is granted, in the second stage it is possible to obtain a **regular legal status** (Kraler, 2009). All *residence permits issued for exceptional circumstances* are limited to a maximum of 12 months. Only the *special protection residence permit* can be renewed. The granting of residence permit for exceptional circumstances is based on case-by-case assessment and not the norm (Asylum Act § 54).

Tolerated persons receive an ID card for tolerated stay, which is valid for one year and can be extended²². The toleration status does not entitle to access to the labour market, an exception are tolerated persons, who have had labour market access before²³. This can be the case when individuals lose an international

²² The toleration ID card will be withdrawn if its period of validity has expired; the requirements for toleration are not or are no longer met; the photograph on the card no longer clearly identifies the holder; or other official entries on the card have become illegible (Aliens Police Act § 46a, n.d.).

²³ Unlike foreigners with protection status, asylum seekers do not have general access to the labour market. In the first three months after admission to the procedure, no work permit may be issued to asylum seekers. If there is still no legally binding decision on the asylum application after this period, an employment permit can be issued to asylum seekers. Between 2004 and 2021, when the Constitutional Court ruled these directives unconstitutional employment

protection status (e.g. due to criminal conviction) and cannot return. They can access the labour market with an employment permit²⁴. Persons who have had their residence permit withdrawn but cannot leave the country and are granted toleration status can also not apply for the *residence permit for special protection* after one year and therefore, have no perspective of regularisation (Hinterberger, 2018).

The prerequisites required for each of the three different residence permits vary:

1. For permits on grounds of Article 8 ECHR (Asylum Act 2005 § 55, 2022) the private / family interests of the person in remaining is balanced against the interests of Austria in removing the person from the country. Factors to be considered include the type, duration and lawfulness of the residence, the actual existence of a family life, the worthiness of protection of the private life, the degree of integration²⁵, the ties to the home country and the criminal record.
2. For permits on grounds of particularly exceptional cases (Asylum Act 2005 § 56, 2022) a proof of five years of continuous residence (at least three years of the total duration of residence must have been legal) are required. Additional factors considered in the decision are the degree of integration, the legal right to accommodation, sufficient health insurance and regular income.
3. For special protection permits (Asylum Act 2005 § 57, 2022) the applicant needs to be witness or victim of human trafficking, of transnational prostitution trafficking or a victim of violence in the family or a person who has already had a tolerated status for one year (Hinterberger, 2018, 2023; Unternehmensservice Portal, 2023).

Residence permits for exceptional circumstances are granted to third-country nationals as:

Residence permit plus (“Aufenthaltsberechtigung plus”), which entitles the holder to reside in Austria and allows unrestricted labour market access. Third-country nationals are eligible for a **residence permit plus** if they fulfill the conditions required for a residence permit on grounds of Article 8 ECHR or if they meet the requirements for a residence permit in particularly exceptional cases **and** if they have successfully completed Module 1 of the Integration Agreement in accordance with the Integration Act or be in permitted gainful employment (Bassermann, 2019; Hinterberger, 2018, 2023).

If third-country nationals are eligible for a residence permit on ground of Article 8 ECHR or fulfill the conditions for particularly exceptional cases but have not completed Module 1 of the Integration Agreement or are in gainful employment ²⁶, they are granted a **standard residence permit** (“Aufenthaltsberechtigung”), with restricted labour market access (employment permit and labour market test required). The **special protection residence permit**, with restricted labour market access (employment

of asylum seekers was restricted to seasonal work. The end of restrictions is still not widely known. Generally, the share of asylum seekers employed is relatively limited.

²⁴ Unlike migrants with protection status, asylum seekers do not have general access to the labour market. In the first three months after admission to the procedure, no employment permit may be issued to asylum seekers. If there is still no legally binding decision on the asylum application after this period, an employment permit can be issued to asylum seekers. In practice, this mainly happens in the area of seasonal work.

²⁵ The examination of the degree of integration of a third-country national comprehends the factors: their ability to maintain oneself, education and vocational training, employment and knowledge of the German language. The proof of one or more requirements can also be provided by submitting a single sponsorship declaration (Asylum Act 2005 § 56, 2022).

²⁶ On the one hand, it must be considered that regular and irregular statuses are not static but can change or alternate. Thus, there are different case constellations, such as people who have spent a few years in Austria regularly and then became irregular resident (e.g. overstayers), or were irregular in between, but were then able to regularize their stay again but are in a precarious residence situation. Considering the differing circumstances, it is possible that a person has already completed Integration Module 1 or is in regular employment at the time of application.

permit required, no labour market screening needed) (Hinterberger, 2018, 2023)²⁷ (Asylum Act 2005 § 54, 2022; Asylum Act 2005 § 55, 2022; Asylum Act 2005 § 56, 2022; Asylum Act 2005 § 57, 2022). The conditions to be eligible are described above.

In the case of restricted labour market access (standard residence permit and special protection residence permit) an employment permit and sometimes labour market test is required. The employment permit is issued to the employer and entitles him to employ the foreign worker specifically applied for in a designated workplace. The application for the employment permit must be submitted by the employer to the regional office of the AMS (Public Employment Service Austria). The employment permit is only issued to foreigners who already have a residence permit or enjoy freedom of settlement but require additional authorization to start employment. The employment permit may only be issued if there is neither a resident nor a foreigner available on the labor market who is willing and able to carry out the requested employment under the conditions permitted by law under the so-called replacement procedure (“Ersatzkraftverfahren”) (AMS (Public Employment Service Austria), n.d.).

In general, holders of *residence permits for exceptional circumstances* have the option to apply for a *Red-White-Red Card plus*²⁸, in the case of *special protection residence permit* the possible claim is also assessed ex officio in the process of renewal (Hinterberger, 2023). *Residence permits for exceptional circumstances* are also an opportunity for third-country nationals from safe countries of origin, whose asylum applications will most likely be rejected (Expert interview 04, 06/2023), to regularise their stay in Austria under the already mentioned prerequisites.

Bilateral agreements and cooperation with third countries linked to readmission²⁹

Cooperations with other countries (especially in the Balkans) to disrupt migration routes from southeastern to central Europe are among the policy priorities of Austria of the last years (Biffl, 2017). As a corollary, Security Partnerships and Memoranda of understanding were implemented. Examples are the “Vienna Declaration” and “Prague Declaration” and the establishment of the Joint Coordination Platform in 2021³⁰.

Related to the implementation of return decisions, different **agreements/arrangements** with third countries linked to readmission have to be considered. Irrespective of whether these

²⁷ An exception are minors in the care of foster parents or a youth welfare agency and enjoy special protection. They can immediately obtain a Red-White-Red Card plus with free labor market access (Hinterberger, 2023; Unternehmensservice Portal, 2023).

²⁸ Requirements are: language competence at A2 level, legal entitlement to accommodation, adequate health insurance and that the stay is not a financial burden for the state.

²⁹ This sub section draws on the Expert interview 06, with a representative of Department Return, Reintegration and Quality Development of the Federal Ministry of the Interior in March 2024.

³⁰ 2020 eighteen countries adopted the Vienna Declaration, in which they agreed to create a platform for coordinating the fight against illegal migration along the eastern Mediterranean routes. The JCP is intended to coordinate measures and cooperation in the key areas of border protection, return, asylum procedures and the fight against human smuggling and started its work 2021. In the Prague Declaration (2021) on political guidelines for the Joint Coordination Platform (JCP) on combating irregular migration along the Eastern Mediterranean route, the Ministers and representatives of the Western Balkans, the Salzburg Forum, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Switzerland in the presence of the European Commission, EASO, Frontex, Europol, ICMPD, IOM, UNHCR and the representatives of the Secretariat of the Joint Coordination Platform (JCP) have met to further improve and extend cooperation activities (Austrian delegation, 2020; PRAGUE DECLARATION ON POLITICAL GUIDELINES FOR THE JOINT COORDINATION PLATFORM on Effectively Combating Irregular Migration along the Eastern Mediterranean Route, 2021).

agreements/arrangements are legally binding or not, they represent a central instrument for shaping the cooperation with the countries of origin and the associated processes in mutual agreement.

Particularly in cases where no travel documents are available and no unaccompanied returns can be carried out, the readmission readiness of the countries of origin and practical readmission cooperation in the various phases of return preparation are of great importance. By and large, readmission agreements are therefore as much an expression of an already good cooperation as they facilitate it, with their legal form being of secondary role.

Exchange and dialogue mechanisms with third countries represent a key level of the practical implementation of readmission. These can take different forms depending on the type of agreement. While the exchange within the framework of EU readmission agreements is formalised in the form of Joint Working Groups with representation of the third-country and the European Commission, which exchange information once a year, the type of exchange in bilateral agreements is defined specifically, often in the form of working groups, the holding of which is then initiated by the Federal Ministry of the Interior or the partner country. Concerns can also be raised in the form of technical Consular Consultations led by MFA. In most cases, the country representations in Austria are therefore the points of contact and Austria's position as a official seat of the United Nations and host to other relevant organisations (such as OSCE) has facilitated access to and a good cooperation with third-countries and, according to the Ministry of the Interior, is a definitive advantage compared to other EU countries not being in such a position; in others, Austria's representations in the third-country serve as point of contact. There are also opportunities to either invite delegations or visit third countries and seek contact with the responsible representatives. In third countries, as in Austria, there is often a mixture of migration authorities, the Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Practical procedures are discussed in consultation with the BFA. Regarding national practical implementation, the Implementing Protocols are essential for classic readmission agreements concluded at EU level. In addition to the Joint Working Groups at European level, the Country Working Groups, which are convened by Frontex and Member States; and specifically exchange information on certain third countries, are also important at operational level. This is very much about exchanging best practice.

In addition to cooperation and networking of the implementation of agreements and readmission processes in the EU level with so called "like-minded countries". In the case of Austria, there is an exchange within the framework of the so-called DACH cooperation between Germany, Austria and Switzerland³¹, which is also based on systemic comparability and overlaps between the nationalities with which cooperation in the area of return is focused.

In the experience of the Austrian authorities, there is a shift from narrow readmission agreements to more comprehensive agreements also including other areas, such as in the case of Austria's Migration and Mobility Partnership Agreement of 2023, which includes readmission, but also takes other topics in the field of migration into account. Further agreements signed in 2023 include the protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Republic of Armenia on the implementation of the Agreement between the European Union and the Republic of Armenia on the readmission of persons residing without authorization; and a (not legally binding) joint declaration between the Kingdom of

³¹ The name DACH derives from the vehicle codes for Germany (D), Austria (A) and Switzerland (CH). „DACH“ cooperations also exist in other policy areas, including research and innovation, education, or defence, to name but a few. Unlike the Nordic cooperation, there is no formalised umbrella.

Morocco and the Republic of Austria aimed at preventing further irregular migration and at enhancing return cooperation.³²

Austria's recent readmission agreements reflect the changing composition of asylum applicants with a low probability of remaining in the country. Table 8 in the ANNEX lists the top twenty countries of citizenship of third-country nationals who have left the territory of Austria to a third-country (country of citizenship or other third-country) and of third-country nationals ordered to leave between 2017 and 2022 (EUROSTAT³³). The return rate (RR) used is taken from the EU return dashboard.³⁴ In the following, peculiarities, continuities and changes of the countries of citizenship of third-country nationals who have left the territory of Austria to a third-country (country of citizenship or other third-country) and of third-country nationals ordered to leave between 2017 and 2022 are discussed. Additionally, the return rate is related to existing agreements with third countries.

Continuities

Among third – country nationals ordered to leave, Serbian and Afghan citizens are leading until 2020, in 2021 Morocco is in second place between Serbia and Afghanistan, in 2021 the three leading countries are Tunisia, India and Pakistan, Serbia in fifth place. In all years, Serbian citizens are the most strongly represented among the third-country nationals returned, following an order to leave (OTL). Albania and Georgia, Russia, China incl. Hong Kong and Nigeria and, since 2019, Bosnia and Herzegovina are also always among the top ten countries of origin in these years.

In general, Serbian citizens who have received an order to leave and are returning to a third-country, are represented to a high degree in all categories. Except for 2020 (RR 88%), which could be due to Covid-19 and the associated mobility restrictions, the return rate is 100% in all other years and is therefore well above the EU average.

Also consistently represented among the top twenty countries of citizenship in all categories are citizens from Bosnia and Herzegovina. Their numbers are considerably lower than those of third-country nationals with Serbian citizenship. Here too, the return rate is 100% in four out of the five years assessed (2021: 90%).

In the following list, a distinction is made between countries with and without a bilateral agreement linked to readmission with Austria, as well as a low (0-25%), average (26-50%), high (51-75%) and very high (76-100%) return rate. The division of the return rate into the categories low, average, high and very high is carried out in this form with reference to the Austrian return rate between 2017 and 2022, which ranges between 20% (2022) and 65% (2017) and reaches a maximum of 50% except for the years 2017 and 2018 (over 60%, also an exception with regard to the earlier years). The (traditionally calculated) average return rate between 2010 and 2022 is 40%. These figures do not consider the high level of complexity and context underlying the return rates in the different years. These are addressed in the following sections.

Further countries ranked within the top twenty countries with (partly) **very high (76-100%) or high return rates (51-75%) and bilateral agreements with Austria on readmission** are:

- **Georgia:** lowest return rate 2019: 68%; highest return rate in 2017, 2020, 2022: 100%
- **North Macedonia:** lowest return rate 2020: 91%; highest return rate 2017, 2018, 2019, 2022: 100%

³² An overview of all bilateral agreements and further agreements linked to readmission, including sources / links, is provided in Table 3 in the ANNEX.

³³ TCNs who have left Austria to a third-country (country of citizenship or other third-country): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_des_custom_12116975/default/table?lang=en

TCNs ordered to leave: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord_custom_8452554/default/table

³⁴ <https://migration-demography-tools.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dashboards/eu-migration-return-msc-and-sacs-perspective>

- **Russia:** highest return rate 2017, 2018: 100%; from 2019, the figures decrease and range between 51% (2020) and 59% (2021)
- The return rate of **Nigeria** is mainly increasing since 2017 (38%), lowest return rate 2018: 35%; highest return rate 54% (2022).
- **Ukraine:** until 2021 (lowest return rate 2019: 75%; highest return rate: 2017, 2018, 2020: 100%
- **Kosovo:** lowest return rate 2020: 71%; highest return rate 2017, 2018, 2019, 2022: 100%
- **Albania:** lowest return rate 2020: 97%; highest return rate 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021, 2022: 100%
- **Moldova:** lowest return rate 2022 (55%), highest return rate 2018, 2020, 2021: 100%

Bilateral agreement, but (partly) low return rate (0-25%): Although there is a bilateral agreement with Tunisia since 1965, and for the years 2017 (59%) and 2019 (57%) the return rate was over 55%, it decreased afterwards with the lowest value 2022 (1%) (2020: 25%, 2021: 10%).

No bilateral agreement (or since 2023), but (partly) very high and high return rate:

- China incl. Hong Kong (in all years a return rate of 100%) – in contrast to other EU countries, where return rates averaged between 20% and 30%.
- **Syria:** lowest return rate 2020: 14%; highest return rate 2018, 2022: 100%
- **Iran:** lowest return rate 2020: 13%; highest return rate 2017: 100%; between 2018 and 2022 between 20% (2020) and 54% (2022)
- The **Iraq** is among those countries with a high number of orders to leave issued in all years; in 2017 and 2018, the return rates are above 80%, but decrease significantly in the following years (2019: 26%, 2020: 14%, 2021: 23%) increasing slightly again 2022 (34%) (bilateral agreement since 2023).
- **Turkiye:** lowest return rate 2021, 2022: 65%; highest return rate 2018: 100%
- **Armenia:** lowest return rate 2021: 52%; highest return rate 2018: 89% (bilateral agreement since 2023).

(Partly) low (0-25%) and average return rate (26-50%), no bilateral agreements with Austria (or since 2023):

- **Algeria:** between 2017 and 2019 between 48% (2017) and 66% (2018), then decrease on Austrian and EU level, lowest 2% (2021); highest 10% (2022)
- **Pakistan:** highest return rate 2018: 27%, especially decreasing since 2021 (7%), 2022 only 1%, but third-country in the list of issued orders to leave
- **India:** 2017: 25%, 2018: 40%, 2019: 41% 2020: 25%, 2021: 15%, 2022: 5% (bilateral agreement since 2023)
- **Morocco:** between 2017 and 2019 higher or very close to the return rate on EU level, between 31% (2019) and 50% (2018), than decrease 2021 and 2022: 1%. (joint declaration since 2023)
- **Bangladesh:** highest return rate 2018: 43%, which is a lot higher than the average return rate of other EU member states (10%), than decrease, lowest return rate 2020 and 2022: 4%.
- **Egypt:** highest return rate 2019 (55%), strong decrease 2021 (8%) and 2022 (9%)

For the following explanations, particularly in Section 2, a focus is placed on the period between 2016 and 2022, as well as on those countries of citizenship that accounted for at least 50 percent of orders to leave in these years. The proposed focus on those countries of citizenship that accounted for 50 percent of the orders to leave in the last four years (2018-2022) was extended for the following reasons:

- The changes to be considered in the top ranked countries of citizenship among asylum applications and related categories, such as orders to leave, in 2022. The year 2022 shows extensive and significant changes compared to previous years that were not previously apparent and whose continuation for the following years is still open. These changes mainly concern the number of applications for international protection and related categories, and in particular the composition of countries of

citizenship in all categories (applications and decisions for international protection, orders to leave issued, migrants returned, following an order to leave).

- Furthermore, the longer time period supports the inclusion of continuously relevant countries of citizenship represented among orders to leave, which would not be included if limited to the last four years.

These countries are further referred to in the text as the 50 percent selection. A list of these countries, including Albania, Afghanistan, Turkey, Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Nigeria, Bangladesh, Serbia, India, Pakistan, Tunisia, and Iraq can be found in Table 9: Overview of first time asylum applicants, first instance positive decisions and rejected asylum applications, third-country nationals ordered to leave, third-country nationals returned to a third-country following an order to leave and of the return rate between 2016 and 2022 (50 percent selection of countries of citizenship acc. OTL) (EUROSTAT)Table 8 in the ANNEX. Particularly regarding the 50% selection of countries of citizenship, the type of agreement procedure provides additional insights into the understanding of country-specific return rates. The overview provided in Table 8 (Third-country nationals who have left the territory to a third-country) in the ANNEX illustrates the relevance of EU Readmission Agreements (EURAs) for several countries under the 50 percent selection, namely Albania, Serbia, Turkey, and Pakistan. In these countries of citizenship, there is a 98 to 100 percent match between the number of citizens returned, following an order to leave and the number of persons returned under the EU Readmission Agreement. The sum of the returned under an EU readmission agreement of these countries make a percentage share of 48% in 2018 and of over 50% in the subsequent years of the total (2019: 54%; 2020: 53%; 2021: 57%).

Albania, Serbia and Turkey are countries with a stable and (very) high return rate between 2017 and 2022³⁵, while in the case of Pakistan the return rate varies: while it increased and then remained quite stable from 2016 until 2019, it decreased onwards and dropped to 7% in the years 2021 and 2022. Also noticeable is the high share of unknown returns, which, however, has decreased significantly over the years, especially from 2019 to 2020 (2018: 2 108; 2019: 1 132; 2020: 40 and 2021: 95). Regarding third-country nationals who returned under another readmission agreement Nigeria, Afghanistan and Bangladesh are the only countries of the 50 percent selection under this category, but with a percentage share of the total of returns under other readmission agreements of always over 90% in this period (2018: 92%; 2019: 96%; 2020: 96%; 2021: 97%). Regarding third-country nationals who have left the territory to a third-country without an existing readmission agreement, in the year 2018 no returns without an existing readmission agreement are documented by the EUROSTAT³⁶ data, since then numbers increased over the years. With a peak of 1 160 persons 2021, including citizens from Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, Nigeria, India, and Iraq, with together make a share of 33% of the total of this category. Developments of the recent years illustrate a higher representation of countries of citizenship of the 50percent selection according to orders to leave 2020 and 2021. 2020 All named countries except Tunisia are also represented in this category, making a percentage share of 24% of the total returns without readmission agreement. 2019 only Iraqi citizens are represented, which, however, already account for 45% of the total. 2018 no countries are named under this category and the total is zero.

Impacting events whose effects on the composition of affected third-country nationals and their return to the country of citizenship or to another third-country and thus the return rate must be taken into account are the COVID-19 pandemic (2020 to June 2023) and related mobility restrictions, the refugee crisis 2015/2016 and related legal tightening of regulations (e.g. Amendment of the Asylum Act, 2016; Aliens Law Amendment Act,

³⁵ All mentioned returned rates are listed in Table 7 in the ANNEX.

³⁶ TCNs who have left the territory to a third-country by type of agreement procedure and citizenship: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_agr_custom_12117205/default/table?lang=en

2017; Basic Act on Social Assistance, 2019)³⁷, the Ukraine war (February 2022), the Taliban takeover in Afghanistan (August 2021) as well as the lifting of visa requirements in Serbia, which allowed visa-free entry for Indian citizens from 2017 until January 1, 2023 and Tunisian citizens until Nov 2022 (BMI, 2023).

However, an assessment of agreements linked to readmission based on the return rate falls short in many respects. Another instrument for evaluating cooperation is the indicators collected by the EU member states as part of the visa leverage mechanism. Article 25a of the Visa Code entered into force on 02.02.2020. The Visa Leverage Mechanism provides for measures to be taken in connection with the issuing of Schengen visas, depending on the level of readmission cooperation. These can be facilitations for those states that cooperate well, or difficulties such as sanctions for states that do not cooperate. However, to achieve a valid result here, the Member States are required to provide quantitative information monthly and on the qualitative factors once a year. This means that all member states submit quantitative factors monthly, and once a year the member states are required to submit a comprehensive qualitative assessment on readmission cooperation. This qualitative assessment, in addition to the quantitative indicators, allows a more meaningful evaluation of cooperation with third countries or countries of origin in this area.

The added value of the broader qualitative assessment is that this clarifies what needs to be considered in order to read these figures and thus arrive at a valid value. In addition, many other factors, e.g. onward mobility, must be taken into account, but are not factored into the calculation of the return rate. Other factors that can lead to a distortion of the return rate include legal issues, such as an application for residence permits for exceptional circumstances, humanitarian issues, other changes in legal requirements or medical reasons, with the issue of the person's ineligibility carrying the greatest weight. There are therefore many possible influencing factors between a return decision and operational implementation³⁸.

Other indicators of a functioning readmission agreement are cooperation in voluntary and forced returns, whereby the focus is always on voluntary returns, responding to requests for identification or the issuing of replacement travel documents, or cooperation in the implementation of charter flights. These are qualitative criteria, but they are essential for the evaluation of agreements.

Another point is the lack of insight into whether and where people have already received a return decision. In contrast to Dublin, where the comparison takes place immediately and an internal system makes it possible to determine responsibilities, until recently it was almost impossible to determine whether, for example, several return decisions existed for one person. Since the SIS Return Regulation came into force (2023), return decisions can be tracked, even if the implementation of the system is still in its infancy and mutual recognition of the return decision has not yet been implemented.

³⁷ The impact of the refugee crisis 2015/2016 and related legal changes are already described in Section 1.

³⁸ For illustration: Due to visa-free entry to Serbia in 2022, there was a very high number of asylum applications from Tunisian nationals in Austria. Many of these applications were either not admitted at all in the fast-track procedure, and then there are many negative procedures and return decisions. In addition, many people are no longer in Austria until a few days after submitting their application but are counted. The procedures have been completed in Austria. In the case of Tunisia in particular, Aa comparison of the return decisions and the actual returns results in a distorted picture, as the whereabouts of many of the people concerned were not known to the authorities shortly after. It must be assumed that they are no longer in have left Austria without waiting for the outcome of their procedure.

SECTION 2: Statistical description of the context

Data on irregular migration and return

Section 2 provides an overview of existing estimates and indicators on Austria's irregular migrant population. Starting with a description of existing estimates, it goes on to discuss asylum application figures, positive and negative decisions, third-country nationals ordered to leave, and third-country nationals returned following an order to leave. The apprehensions of irregularly present third-country nationals are also included, before the development of return rates is addressed. As possible impacting factors on the return rate, the development of the granting of the different types of status (incl. toleration) is discussed with reference to Austria's formal regularisation tools described in Section 1. In the concluding two sections, characteristics of third-country nationals ordered to leave and returned following an order to leave are described, and data on the types of return are analysed. Data description and analysis refers to Austria's policy priorities, impacting events, changes of the legislative framework and the country specific framework, especially the institutional setting and stakeholder landscape.

The irregular migrant population in Austria - Estimates

In the Austrian case, no estimates of the flows of irregular migrants are available. Instead border apprehensions and asylum applications have been commonly used in public and policy debate, despite the problems associated with the conflation of irregular entry and subsequent irregular stay on the one hand, and asylum and migrant irregularity, on the other (Savatic et al., 2024).

In regard to the stocks of the irregular migrant population two approaches have been used for some time, both based on a method developed in the Clandestino project, a research project funded under the sixth EU framework programme for research and technological innovation.

The Clandestino estimates:

The Clandestino estimate) provided the first estimate for Austria following a transparent scientific method. It covers the years years 2001-2008 (Jandl, 2009). The estimate is based on a multiplier method (Rodriguez-Sanchez & Tjaden, 2023, p. 14f), using Police Crime Statistics as the basis for calculating a multiplier. This dataset published annually is unique as it covers both nationals and non-nationals and includes information on reported offences and suspects by criminal acts as well as on the residence status of suspects (Bundeskriminalamt, n.d.; Jandl, 2009). The basic idea of the estimate is to use the share of irregular migrants amongst crime suspects as a basis for extrapolating their share in the total population.

To derive the multiplier, the data was adjusted to to account for

- Offence categories that mainly apply to foreigners / are directly related to irregular migration (e.g. falsification of documents, fake marriages to obtain residence permit, human smuggling)
- So-called "criminal tourists", i.e. foreign nationals not actually residing in Austria.

In addition, differences in control rates between foreign nationals and citizens due to profiling as well as in regard to the socio-economic characteristics of the national and foreign populations need have been taken into account to choose the maximum and minimum estimate. Other adjustments relate to persons with an unknown residence status and the exclusion of EU nationals and other EEA citizens from the estimate.

Based on this calculated base figures, a range of multipliers is calculated by relating the adjusted crime suspects figures to the relevant population figures. For the calculation of an upper limit for the share of crime suspects among the illegally resident population, the figure on adjusted foreign resident suspects is divided by the registered foreign resident population. For the calculation of the lower limit the equivalent

are divided for the population of Austrian nationals (Jandl, 2009). Since there were no detailed crime suspects data for the years 2001-2003 and for 2008, Jandl extrapolated numbers for these years by the calculated multipliers. Results are illustrated in the following table, taken from Jandl, 2009:

Table 1: Estimates on the irregularly resident population in Austria, taken from Jandl (2009)

YEAR	Max. estimate	Min. estimate	Central estimate
2001	115.687	39.456	77.572
2002	86.964	29.660	58.312
2003	84.837	28.934	56.886
2004	95.027	30.934	62.980
2005	73.838	25.174	49.506
2006	67.978	22.905	45.442
2007	63.504	22.981	43.243
2008	54.064	18.439	36.252

Note: value for 2004 reflects pre-EU-Enlargement

The estimates suggest a continuous decline of the irregular resident population for the period covered, which is plausible given the two waves of EU enlargement in 2004 and 2007 and a temporary decline of asylum applications.

Estimate of the Statistic AUSTRIA for the purpose of the usually resident population (EUROSTAT)

Statistic Austria provides EUROSTAT with an estimation of the usually resident population based on the Central Residence Register (CRR) of the Ministry of Interior and stored in a statistical “mirror” register, i.e. an anonymised version of the CRR (POPREG - population register). In contrast to the original administrative data, which only stores the latest valid information and therefore does not allow linkages of all records of a single person, the POPREG database stores historical data on an individual level, using a unique identifier for each person (Statistics Austria, 2023). Linkage is also possible with other registers. In July 2022 Statistics Austria launched the Austrian Micro Data Centre (AMDC), through which public authorities can provide register data in anonymised format for research purposes, while the academic community can access a wide range of linked register data for data analysis. To date, migration related registers are not systematically linked to the AMDC, nor are they normally accessible to researchers, although linked analyses have been undertaken in the context of projects commissioned by the Austrian Integration Fund (See for the most recent of a series of three studies Endel et al., 2022). Data linkage could, in theory, provide solid information on individual’s legal status trajectories as well as on the stock of persons issued an order to leave, duration of stay and other aspects.

Population and Migration Statistics (ex-post-analysis) are based on pseudonymised microdata on registrations and de-registrations. Furthermore, as part of an annual *residence analysis* aimed at determining the municipal population figures for tax sharing, different data bases (including among others the residence register, social security register, tax register, social benefits database) are compared to identify potential nominal members and to adjust the population register.

For Eurostat’s dataset on the usual resident population (URESPOP)³⁹ which follows the de facto concept Statistics Austria estimates the over- and undercoverage, systematically assessing ‘overcovered’ groups (such as students studying abroad keeping their legal residence in Austria or persons with a legal residence

³⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/view/demo_urespop.

in more than one country) and undercoverage. The latter also includes unregistered migrants, including unregistered irregular migrants.

The non-registered population is considered as sub-group difficult to measure.⁴⁰ The Statistics Austria's estimation method is based on the methodology developed by Jandl (2009, see description above). Unlike the Clandestino estimate, EU citizens are not excluded due to the interest to capture non-registered EU-citizens too. The resulting estimate (or rather range) is the starting point for the further assumption of how many people are not registered. As the logic of the URESPOP database requires a point estimate, the Statistics Austria estimate uses the average (the "central estimate" in Jandl's estimation).

As an estimate of resident irregular migrant population, the estimate is limited in two ways: The population register might contain residents without legal status or expired residence permit, as registration does not involve a check of the legal status of the person.⁴¹ Yet because it is difficult to remain undetected by authorities for a long period of time and persons can be deregistered ex officio, the number is likely to be small. A second, more serious limitation is that the method does not address duration of stay. As a result, the method is vulnerable to extreme, temporal fluctuations of largely temporally staying irregular migrants. Considering that only a certain (unknown) share of the number of irregular migrants estimated according to the Clandestino multiplier method will actually be a usual resident according to the definition of usual residents according to EU and international standards (one year rule) the Statistics Austria estimate assumes that half of those estimated according to the methodology developed by Jandl can be considered long term resident, leading to a rough number of 62 000 non-registered people present for more than twelve months in Austria in 2022 (Statistics Austria, 2023).⁴²

Discussion: Trends in irregular migrant stocks

As the Clandestino and the Statistics Austria estimates concern different target groups (irregular third-country nationals present on the territory irrespective of length of stay vs. all unregistered persons, including EU citizens staying for at least one year) they are not directly comparable. Nevertheless, and adjusting the two estimates to make them comparable, it is clear that the estimated stocks of irregular migrants has increased.⁴³

Table 2: Estimates of the irregular Migrant Population, 2008 and 2022

⁴⁰ Information exists on specific categories, such as persons with diplomatic staff/employees of international organisations based in Vienna. These are separately accounted for.

⁴¹ Unlike in Spain, the registration register (on which the statistical population register is based) can be used by immigration authorities for checks. Also, in practice, officials at the municipal registration offices might ask for additional documents. From the perspective of migrants therefore, there are risks involved – as are potential benefits.

⁴² National metadata for the URESPOP dataset was released by Eurostat for the first time only in October 2023 (for the year 2022). This documentation also contains the calculation of the population figure by Statistics Austria. No other country provides a similar level of detail.

⁴³ In 2008, 24% of foreign suspects marked as irregularly staying in the Police Crime Statistics were EU nationals. Adjusting the central estimate for Austria for 2008 gives a figure of some 45,000 unregistered persons. Applying the assumption that only 50% of these are staying more than a year, the resulting stock is 22,5200, with the Statistics Austria estimate for 2022 (62,000) being almost 2.8 times higher than the 2008 estimate. Conversely, using the calculated share of third-country nationals in all crime suspects with an irregular stay for 2022 (70.35%) the number of third-country nationals amongst the 62,000 unregistered persons is some 43,600, thus only 2.4 times the number of those estimated during Clandestino (18,130).

	2008 (Clandestino)	As share of total foreign population in 2008	2022 (Statistics Austria)	As share of total foreign population in 2022
Unregistered population, without residence assumption	45,000	5.33%	124,000	7.43%
Unregistered population (EU and non-EU), staying for at least a year	22,500	2.66%	62,000	3.71%
Unregistered third- country nationals, staying for at least a year (rounded)	18,130	2.15%	43,600	2.61%

Source: Own calculations based on Clandestino and Statistics Austria estimates and Statistics Austria statistics on the total average resident population (Statistik Austria, 2024).

To some extent the increase of might be linked to more volatile flows and significant transit migration. With more migrants passing and more offenses to be reported involving such migrants, the result of the estimate increases, without necessarily reflecting an increased number of irregular migrant residents who stay for a more significant time.⁴⁴ An indication of the vulnerability of the estimation method are the extremely high estimates for 2015 prepared for the advisory council on migration using the original Clandestino method and resulting in a central estimate of some 174,500 (quoted after Kierans et al., 2024). The latter is very likely a reflection of the approximately one million third-country nationals arriving, and for the large part transiting Austria in 2015.⁴⁵

On the other hand, a certain increase of the stock of irregular residents between 2008 and 2022 is also plausible. The decline of the irregular migrant population between 2001 and 2008 found by Clandestino is largely a reflection of EU-enlargement, the significant share of irregularly staying migrants from accession countries in Austria at the beginning of the 2000s and their ex lege regularisation as a consequence of EU accession. By 2022, the composition of the irregular migrant population will have changed, reflecting both a higher share of migrants from visa-free countries in the Western Balkans, reflected amongst others in return statistics and a higher number of persons associated in some way or another to asylum related inflows. However, considering the significant increase of the foreign resident population during this period – it almost doubled from 844,580 in 2008 to 1,669,348 in 2022 (Statistik Austria, 2024), the share of the (long term) irregular migrant population in the total number of foreign residents has only slightly increased, from 2.15% to 2.61%.⁴⁶

Nevertheless, onward migration has also considerably increased, especially relating to persons associated to asylum. One indication of the significance of onward migration is the large gap between asylum applications and asylum seekers in basic care. Thus in 2022, altogether 122,272 asylum applications were submitted in Austria – an all time high by far exceeding the number of applications submitted at the height of the refugee crisis in 2015 (88,160), but only 21,572 asylum seekers were in the Basic Care System at the

⁴⁴ For national purposes, every person staying more than 90 days is counted towards the resident population. 90 days thus provides a benchmark to distinguish people temporarily on the move or in transit from migrants.

⁴⁵ The figure was reported by the person responsible for the apprehension database at a MIrreM data workshop in September 2023.

⁴⁶ Own estimate, based on the rough estimation presented in FN 43.

end of the year, or on average an estimated 18,600).⁴⁷ Considering the average duration of asylum procedures between 2021 and 2023 (about 4.5 months), a total ‘throughput’ of some 50,000 persons can be estimated.⁴⁸ However, in 48% of cases, applications were otherwise closed (BFA, 2023b), largely because of absconding, and presumably, onward migration. Another indication is the relatively stable number of the Afghan resident population, despite a very high volume of asylum related inflows and a far lower number of return decisions. Thus, between 2017 and 2023 the Afghan population has only grown by 4500, despite some 54,000 asylum applications by Afghan nationals in the same period. Yet only 12,000 of these were recorded as immigrants based on the population registration, while some 10,200 were recorded as emigrants, leaving a large number of persons unaccounted for (Rosner, 2024).

Irregular migration and return in the context of asylum

In Austria policy priorities, the political, media and society discourse, changes of the legislative framework as well as migration related measures illustrate a thematic interlinkage between asylum, irregular migration and return. The following section looks at developments in the number of asylum applications, rejections, orders to leave and third-country nationals returned, following an order to leave in the period between 2010 and 2022, with a focus on the period from 2015 onwards. Data analysis is limited by missing or inaccessible data and meta-information on existing data on EUROSTAT or of national data sources. Data gaps, loss and the different national databases are discussed in Section 3.

Figure 11: Asylum applicants (including first instance applicants and subsequent applicants), first instance decisions on applications: rejections of asylum applications and the total of positive decisions (including positive decisions on a Geneva convention status, subsidiary protection status and humanitarian status) between 2011 and 2022. (EUROSTAT) (in the ANNEX) shows the development of numbers of asylum applicants (including first instance applicants and subsequent applicants), rejections of asylum applications and the total of positive decisions (including positive decisions on a Geneva convention status, subsidiary protection status and humanitarian status between 2011 and 2022).

While between 2011 and 2013 numbers of asylum applicants, rejections and positive decisions (total) were stable, and rejections were consistently more than double the number of positive decisions, there was an initial increase in asylum applicants from 17,500 (2013) to 28,035 in 2014, and in the same period rejections fell from 11 690 to 2 230, and positive decisions rose (from 4 920 to 7 175). In 2015 the number of asylum applicants multiplied to 88,160, positive decisions (15,045) were more than twice as high as in 2014, but rejections also increased significantly (6,050). The number of asylum applicants more than halved in 2016, with positive decisions peaking at 30,370 during this period and rejections also almost doubling. Finally, a further sharp decline in the number of asylum applications can be observed in 2017, with the number of asylum applications being slightly lower than the number of positive decisions in both this year and 2018, reflecting the increasing duration of asylum procedures following the 2015 crisis.⁴⁹ Rejections also rose

⁴⁷ Calculated on the basis of data for 31/12/2021, 01/07/2022 and 31/12/2022. No detailed data by month was available.

⁴⁸ Own estimate, applying a multiplier derived from the share of the average duration of procedures in the calendar year. A large number of persons will have been in basic care only for a couple of days.

⁴⁹ Between the 1st quarter of 2016 and the 3rd quarter of 2018 the average duration of asylum procedures increased from 7.4 months to a peak of 21.6 months. By the 4th quarter of 2021 the average duration had decreased to 3.9 months (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2023, p. 15f), further decreasing to 3.6 months on average in 2022 and increasing again to 5.5 months on average in 2023 (BFA, 2023b, 2024). In a similar vein, the number of cases with an average duration longer than 6 months exceeded those with a shorter duration between 2016 and 2018, highlighting the mounting backlog of cases that only got reduced afterwards (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2023, p. 15f). Note that these

again from 2016 to 2017 by 7,915 (19,960 in total) and remained at this level in 2018. This year is also the only one since 2013 in this period in which rejections again outweigh positive decisions. The number of asylum applicants in 2018 was the lowest since the crisis with 13,710 applications. Applications remained relatively stable until 2020, after which numbers rose again to 39,900 in 2021 and to a peak of over 112,000 applications in 2022. In 2019, the number of asylum applicants again outweighed rejections (6,465) and positive decisions (7,425). Rejections fall slightly in the following year (2020), rise again in 2021 and finally reach a peak of 22,440 in 2022, again exceeding the number of positive decisions (16,560) in that year. In 2023 (not included in this figure), the number of asylum applications almost halved (58,660 applications) (EUROSTAT)⁵⁰. This downward trend appears to continue in 2024 (January to May 2024 incl.: 11,635 applications) (EUROSTAT)⁵¹.

The following figure 2 provides information on the developments and relation between first instance decisions on applications (total and rejected), third-country nationals ordered to leave and third-country nationals who returned to a third-country (comprehending countries of citizenship and other third countries), following an order to leave.

Figure 2: First instance decisions on applications (total) and rejected first instance decisions (Extra-EU27 (from 2020)⁵²), third-country nationals ordered to leave and returned to a third-country, following an order to leave (EUROSTAT⁵³)

indicators have been specifically provided to the Court of Auditors (Rechnungshof) to compile two reports and are not published in this level of detail normally (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2019, 2023).

⁵⁰ Asylum applicants by type, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza__custom_12220388/default/table?lang=en

⁵¹ Asylum applicants by type, citizenship, age and sex - monthly data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctzm__custom_12220397/default/table?lang=en

⁵² First instance decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfst__custom_11826062/default/table?lang=en

⁵³ TCNs who have left Austria to a third-country, following an order to leave: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1__custom_8547137/default/table

TCNs ordered to leave: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord__custom_8452554/default/table

⁵³ <https://migration-demography-tools.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dashboards/eu-migration-return-msc-and-sacs-perspective>

Two recent reports by the Court of Auditors (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2019, 2023) further shed light on the available indicators of return, examining the effectiveness of the BFA's monitoring system. One concrete outcome was the development of a tiered system distinguishing between three categories (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2019, p. 112): (1) 'transport cases', i.e. persons with a known address, and valid travel documents (passport or travel certificate) and a high probability of being removed (with 1,533 persons on that list on 1 April, 2022), (2) persons in active procedure, i.e. persons with a known address but without travel documents, with a medium probability of being removed (with 4,883 persons on that list on 1 April, 2022) and (3) cold cases, without a known address, hence unlikely to be removed and likely to have absconded abroad (with 55,232 persons being on that list on 1 April 2022) (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2023, p. 46f). As the snapshot of the situation in 2022 shows, the number of active cases (category 1 and 2) was just about 10% of the total number of pending cases, highlighting that the mismatch between return decisions and TCN's returned may be significantly impacted by the high share of cold cases.

Generally, Austria's strategy towards speeding up procedures:

- (1) a general speeding up of asylum procedures by using fast-track procedures ("Schnellverfahren", less than 35 days) and "rapid-procedures (admissibility/return decisions within 72 hours). A focus has also been on closing pending procedures, including by otherwise closing procedures more rapidly. Reflecting these efforts, the share of procedures exceeding 6 months and those decided within 6 months has been reversed since 2019 and have decreased from a peak of 64.7% in 2017 to 16.4% in 2021.⁵⁴
- (2) A prioritisation of enforcing return of migrants with a criminal conviction – their share in enforced returns stood at 45% in 2022.
- (3) Implementing recommendations of the Court of Auditors, notably in view of prioritising 'active' cases and enhancing its internal monitoring and controlling to more effectively allocate resources.

For further illustration, Table 9: Overview of first time asylum applicants, first instance positive decisions and rejected asylum applications, third-country nationals ordered to leave, third-country nationals returned to a third-country following an order to leave and of the return rate between 2016 and 2022 (50 percent selection of countries of citizenship acc. OTL) (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX provides an overview of first time asylum applicants, first instance positive decisions and rejected asylum applications, third-country nationals ordered to leave, third-country nationals returned to a third-country following an order to leave and of the return rate between 2016 and 2022 of the 50 percent selection of countries of citizenship according orders to leave (EUROSTAT). Figure 8 and Figure 10: Third-country nationals returned to a third-country, following an order to leave (50% selection) (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX illustrate the developments of the numbers of third-country nationals ordered to leave and third-country nationals returned following an order to leave of the 50 percent selection of countries of citizenship (according to orders to leave) between 2016 and 2022.

It is noticeable here that a number of countries with a high proportion of orders to leave only account for a small proportion of asylum applicants (and related of the positive and negative decisions). Particularly striking here are some countries of citizenship, which are already continuously and over a longer time strongly represented among the orders to leave, but only appear to a (sometimes very) small extent among the asylum applicants, including in particular Serbia and Albania - countries, which also have a high return rate. Several countries of citizenship illustrate similar patterns, but only in certain time periods. Countries where this difference has continued over a minimum of three years are Algeria, Morocco, Nigeria, India and Pakistan. Further noticeable features are the sharp increase in the number of asylum applications of

⁵⁴ Own calculations based on Rechnungshof (Rechnungshof Österreich, 2023, p. 16)

citizens of the countries Turkey, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, Bangladesh, India and Pakistan in 2021 and 2022, which were for a high share rejected and related orders to leave have also risen sharply.

Although there has been a high increase in the number of asylum applications from Afghanistan, and it should also be noted that Austria has had a high number of asylum applications from Afghan citizens in all years, the number of rejected asylum applications and orders to leave issued has fallen sharply since 2021, i.e. when the Taliban came to power.

Furthermore, data illustrates that asylum applications of many of the 50 percent selection of countries of citizenship decreased after 2016 / 2017, before they rose again in 2019 or 2020 – which corresponds with the already described development of the total of asylum applications in these years. Examples of this are Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Pakistan, India and Iraq. In the case of Iraq, however, it must be noted that the number of asylum applications has not risen to the same extent and that there has been a continuously high number of orders of return from 2017 onwards, with a drop in 2022 (compared to the years 2017 to 2021).

As the data used (EUROSTAT⁵⁵) refer to first time applicants and first-time decisions (the EUROSTAT data on final decisions includes no selection according country of citizenship⁵⁶), it must be pointed out that there is generally no comparability for the individual years, as

1. there are appeals against negative asylum and return decisions, which lead (in the case of the first appeal) to the suspension of return decisions and might have the outcome, that a protection status is granted;
2. applications for tolerated stay or a residence permit for exceptional circumstances might (if this is done in a timely manner, i.e. before a legally valid return decision has been issued) also lead to a suspension of a return decision and a protection status might be granted;
3. return decisions cannot be carried out for legal or factual reasons, which can (but does not have to) be accompanied by the granting of tolerated status;
4. applications for international protection were filed towards the end of the year and the decisions are not reflected in the figures for this year.

Third-country nationals found to be irregularly present and refused entry at the external borders

Apart from a negative asylum application, a return decision is issued if an irregularly staying person is apprehended. However, the available EUROSTAT⁵⁷ data for Austria, as well as national data, do not distinguish where exactly these apprehensions took place (border apprehensions and apprehensions inside

⁵⁵ Asylum applicants by type, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza_custom_8527230/default/table

First instance decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfsta_custom_8527009/default/table

⁵⁶ Final decisions on asylum applications by type of decision - annual data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tps00193_custom_12117621/default/table?lang=en

⁵⁷ Although it is possible to differentiate between different types of apprehension on EUROSTAT (In the external border area; At the border crossing point – at sea, land, air; Between border crossing points - at sea; Between border crossing points - at land; In the inland area), only total figures are available until 2020; in 2021, 530 apprehensions in the Inland area are given (all other categories are zero), in 2022 there are 1425 apprehensions in the external border area (here too, all other categories are given as zero).

Third-country nationals found to be illegally present - annual data (rounded):

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eipre_custom_12117901/default/table?lang=en

the country). Data does not include information on the duration of stay in Austria, or provides information, if a person had a residence status or visa, which for example expired and was not renewed ('overstayers'). Also, national data, which is published in the situation reports on smuggling and human trafficking by the Federal Criminal Police Office, do not include this information⁵⁸.

Figure 3 illustrates a peak of third-country nationals found to be irregularly present in the years 2015 (impacting event: "refugee crisis") as well as in the exceptional year 2022⁵⁹.

Figure 3: Third-country nationals found to be illegally present (total) between 2010 and 2022 (EUROSTAT⁶⁰)

An analysis focusing on the 50 percent selection of countries of citizenship also shows a peak in apprehensions of persons with Afghan (21,645) and Iraqi (13,810) citizenship in 2015, with the figures for Afghanistan remaining high in the following year (12,035). In 2021 and 2022, the number of apprehensions of Afghan nationals peaks again, but there are also massive increases of Indian nationals (19,305) found to be illegally present, followed by Tunisian nationals (11,360), Moroccans (8,425) and Pakistanis (7,255) (see Figure 12: Third-country nationals found to be illegally present per country of citizenship (50% selection) between 2010 and 2022. (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX).

The composition of the leading third-country nationals refused entry at the external borders shows a different picture: Albania is particularly striking here, with a peak in 2017, followed by a sharp drop in refused entries at the external borders, and a renewed increase from 2020. Turkish citizens were also increasingly refused entry at the border, particularly from 2019. Even if an increase in refused entries can be observed in this category in 2022 for many countries, which are also much more strongly represented among the asylum application figures, the increases are particularly noticeable for Albania and Turkey, i.e.

⁵⁸ More information on the situation reports of the Federal Criminal Police Office: Section 3.

⁵⁹ As explained in the subsection *Bilateral agreements and cooperation with third countries linked to readmission* with regard to the year 2022 and the (rejected) asylum applications, orders to leave and return rate of Tunisian citizens, the interpretation of this data and conclusions on causalities must be handled with care and the respective context must be considered.

⁶⁰ Third-country nationals found to be illegally present - annual data (rounded): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eipre_custom_8514193/default/table

countries with low asylum application figures and a low likelihood of remaining (see Figure 13: Third-country nationals refused entry at the external borders by country of citizenship (selection 50%) - annual data (rounded) (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX). The dominant reasons, why third-country nationals (total, not selection) entry is refused at external borders, are that an alert has been issued, the lack of valid visa or residence permit or of valid travel documents. Until 2017 an issued alert was the main reason for refused entries, starting from 2018 until 2022 a lack of valid visa or residence permit is the leading reason, however, additionally 2022 issued alerts and no valid travel document(s) strongly increased (see in the ANNEX).

The data situation and lack of differentiation also illustrate the challenges of reconstructing the stock and flows of irregular migrants, as a regular migration channel can be followed by an irregular stay (e.g. visa overstayers), and irregular entry can also lead to legal status, as in the case of refugees (Vespe et al., 2017). In order to counteract irregular visa overstay and to improve cooperation with third countries in readmission procedures, the visa code can be mentioned as a main element of the eu visa policy. The visa code comprises the procedures and conditions for issuing short-stay visas and also enables restrictive measures (e.g. in the area of visa processing and visa fees) through the visa leverage mechanism if countries do not cooperate sufficiently in the area of readmission (*Visa Policy - European Commission, 2024*). Cross-EU information systems, such as VIS, also play a central role in visa examination procedures. The Visa Information System (VIS) is a system for the exchange of visa data between the Member States of the European Union and associated countries. VIS⁶¹ is also intended to facilitate visa application procedures at external borders, prevent "visa shopping" and promote the fight against fraud. Queries can be made in the VIS by the competent visa authority for the examination of visa applications, as well as for decisions on the issue, refusal, extension, revocation, etc. of a visa. Furthermore, at the external borders and within the territory of the Member States, the competent authorities may carry out searches in the VIS for the purpose of verifying the identity of the visa holder and/or the authenticity of the visa and/or to determine whether a person fulfills the conditions for entry or stay on the territory of a Member State. In addition, asylum authorities are also authorized to consult the VIS for the purpose of examining an asylum application and determining the Member State responsible for processing the asylum application (*Das Visa Informationssystem (VIS) - Visa-Informationssystem - Datenschutzbehörde, n.d.*). In order to prevent irregular border crossings in the future and make it easier to identify visa overstayers, the implementation of the Entry/Exit System (EES) will also bring about changes: an IT system that automatically registers third-country nationals each time they cross an EU external border (Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs, European Commission, n.d.). The European Travel Information and Authorization System (ETIAS), the implementation of which is planned for 2025, is also an automated system that ensures the transmission of security-related information submitted by visa-free third-country nationals prior to travel (*European Travel Information Authorisation System - European Commission, n.d.*).

The development of return rates

As already explained in Section 1, return policy is generally a constant Austrian policy priority. A decision for voluntary return is possible in every step of the procedure and is always defined as the preferred option (Stiller & Humer, 2020). This flexibility and the possibility of choice at different stages of the process distinguishes Austria from many other EU countries. This must also be considered that the voluntary return option is also used during an ongoing asylum procedure, which also results in differences between the national data collection and the data reported to Frontex and EUROSTAT.

⁶¹ The national VIS authority in Austria is the Federal Ministry of the Interior.

Figure 4 provides an overview of the development of return rates of the 50 percent selection according to orders to leave between 2016 and 2022.

Figure 4: Overview of the development of return rates of the 50 percent selection of countries of citizenship according orders to leave between 2016 and 2022⁶².

The trends in return rates demonstrate that an increase in return rates after 2016 can be observed in all countries of citizenship, with the exceptions of Iraq and Afghanistan - their return rate in 2016 was 100 percent. In the case of Afghanistan, the return rate has fallen significantly, with the lowest return rate in 2020 (8%) and the highest in 2017 (25%). In the case of Iraq, the return rate in 2017 and 2018 was still over 80% and then fell in the following years.

In Albania, Serbia and Turkey, on the other hand, the return rate increased sharply from 2016 to 2017 and remained at a consistently high level in the following years. Strong fluctuations can be seen in the countries of citizenship Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, Bangladesh, India and Pakistan, whereby the changes in 2021 and 2022 are partly decisive here, in which the return rates in the case of Algeria, Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia, Bangladesh, India and Pakistan fell to below 10%.

As already outlined in the subsection *Bilateral agreements and cooperation with third countries linked to readmission*, the (development of) the return rate is not sufficient to draw conclusions about, for example,

⁶² calculated by the provided tool of the EU return dashboard (<https://migration-demography-tools.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dashboards/eu-migration-return-msc-and-sacs-perspective>, accessed November 2023).

improvements in the implementation of return decisions and cooperation with third countries; a number of other qualitative factors must also be taken into account.

Types of positive decisions

In the process of the issuance of a return decision that is interlinked (as one of several options⁶³) with a negative decision on an asylum application, there are several pathways that may lead to a residence permit for exceptional circumstances⁶⁴. The number of granted (ex officio) and positively decided applications for residence permits for exceptional circumstances is therefore also an impacting factor on the final return rate. The following figure shows the development of numbers of total of positive decisions and rejections, as well as of the type of decision between 2016 and 2022. The residence permits for exceptional circumstances⁶⁵ are included under the EUROSTAT category “Humanitarian status”, only comprehending positive decisions on the humanitarian status related to an asylum application. This represents a relevant difference to the available national data (provided by the Ministry of Interior), which will be discussed further in Section 3.

Figure 5: First instance decisions on applications by type of decision (EUROSTAT⁶⁶)

Data illustrate that, compared to Geneva Protection status and subsidiary protection, humanitarian status is granted to a much lesser extent. This also corresponds to the legislative framework and information of the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum, which emphasizes that a residence permit on humanitarian grounds is not the norm, but the exception. It is only granted in special case constellations and is assessed on a case-by-case basis. Furthermore, if a person fulfils the requirements for a residence permit as part of the examination of an asylum application on the grounds of Art. 8 ECHR, no separate application is necessary, as family ties as well as integration steps taken are already taken into account and examined in the asylum procedure (as well as in the appeal procedure of the Federal Administrative Court) (Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum, n.d.-b).

⁶³ Please find further information and an illustration of the process flow from the issuance of a return decision until the return of a third-country national to the country of citizenship or another third-country in Section 1.

⁶⁴ Residence permits for exceptional circumstances are further explained in Section 1.

⁶⁵ Described in Section 1.

⁶⁶ First instance decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfst_a_custom_11826255/default/table?lang=en

Focusing on the 50 percent selection of countries of citizenship Table 10: First instance decisions on applications by type of decision (50% selection) (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX provides an overview first instance decisions on applications by type of decision (EUROSTAT). The comparison of the percentage share of humanitarian status illustrates once again the subordinate importance compared to Geneva Convention status and subsidiary protection status in the majority of the countries of citizenship of the 50% selection, although in individual cases there is a country-specific, mostly limited to certain years, higher significance, such as Serbia (consistently between 40 and 100% of total positive decisions); in 2016 and 2017 for Algeria (100%, not relevant for the other years); Morocco (2016, 2018, 2019, 2020) and Tunisia (2016, 2018). In the case of Nigeria, humanitarian status has the highest significance almost continuously (with the exception of 2021, where it is at the same level as Geneva Convention status at 25%).

The Austrian "toleration" cannot be described as regularisation, but it does suspend the return decision as long as the reasons for the toleration are valid. In addition, a special protection residence permit can be applied for after one year from the tolerated status, so the tolerated status at least opens up the possibility of regularisation. However, the available data suggests that this instrument is handled very restrictively. Data on the granting of tolerated status is also not published in national reports but can be researched - albeit without meta-information - via various parliamentary inquiries (see figure 14 in the ANNEX). Data availability starts 2011 until 2022, the data for the year 2021 is missing. The maximum of toleration cards issued was 355 in 2013, if only complete years are considered, the minimum were 161 toleration cards 2019. 2022 325 toleration cards were issues, 25% percent for Afghan citizens (82 cards). Further information is very limited, 2016 data provided information on the sex of recipients of a toleration ID (82% male and 18% female recipients).

Withdrawals of international protection status (asylum, subsidiary protection or humanitarian status)

On EUROSTAT⁶⁷ data on withdrawals of a protection status is limited (available time period). It comprehends data on decisions withdrawing status granted at first instance decision by type of status withdrawn, citizenship and reason (annual aggregated data) and on decisions withdrawing status granted as final decision in appeal or review by type of status withdrawn is only available since 2021. Since 2022 information on withdrawals is provided by the report on key figures of Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum ("Kennzahlen des BFA") (Ministry of Interior & Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum, n.d.), before that data is only available per parliamentary inquiries⁶⁸. There are differences between the data

⁶⁷ Decisions withdrawing status granted at first instance decision by type of status withdrawn, citizenship and reason - annual aggregated data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asywifsta_custom_8634823/default/table

⁶⁸ https://archiv2022.asyl.at/files/324/04-parl_anfragebeantwortung_subschutz_asyl_aberkenneung_bfa_2018.pdf

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVI/AB/4024/imfname_766738.pdf

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVII/AB/13976/imfname_1555646.pdf

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXIV/AB/7516/fname_211828.pdf

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXIV/AB/5981/fname_194856.pdf

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVII/AB/4878/imfname_931863.pdf

<https://www.parlament.gv.at/gegenstand/XXVII/AB/676>

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVII/AB/9530/imfname_1437598.pdf

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/BR/AB-BR/3345/imfname_740432.pdf

from the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA) and EUROSTAT, as the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum refers to revocation procedures initiated (the top 20 countries are listed by nationality) and issued withdrawal decisions, and a distinction is also made according to the reason for initiation (more comprehensive than in the EUROSTAT data including withdrawn due to revocation, due to ending, due to refusal to renew). The reasons given are a) the residence permit of a reference person was withdrawn⁶⁹; b) in the case of criminal convictions; c) danger to the security of Austria; d) changed circumstances; e) notification of travel movement; f) examination of extension of residence title; g) other. Furthermore, in the national reports only withdrawal procedures based on refugee status or subsidiary protection are listed, while EUROSTAT also includes the humanitarian protection status and a more comprehensive differentiation according to countries of citizenship is possible. However, also in the EUROSTAT database no withdrawals of a humanitarian protection status are stated and all decisions withdrawing the status are assigned to the category (reasons) *Withdrawn due to revocation* (in both data sets: decisions withdrawing status granted at first instance decision and decisions withdrawing status granted as final decision in appeal or review). National data show clear differences between proceedings initiated (2,772) and withdrawal decisions issued (1,086). A difference of 1,686 suggests that in 2022 no withdrawal decision was issued in over 60% of cases, even if proceedings were initiated. The leading reasons why proceedings were initiated at all are criminal offenses (1,434), followed at a considerable distance by the notification of travel movements (539), the category other (276) and changed circumstances (271), the revocation of the status of a reference person (151), the examination of the extension of the residence permit (90) and danger to the security of Austria (7) (BFA, 2023a). The top five nationalities are Syria, the Russian Federation, Afghanistan, Iraq and Iran. Among the top 20 nationalities affected by initiated procedures are some countries of the top 50% selection, such as Serbia, Afghanistan, Iraq, Turkey, Nigeria and Bangladesh. The procedures initiated mainly concern the withdrawal of refugee status (2 161) and, to a lesser extent, subsidiary protection status (611). Regarding the withdrawal decisions issued, 951 decisions to withdraw refugee status and 135 to withdraw subsidiary protection status were issued in 2022. What is striking here is that of the total of 772 notifications issued for the withdrawal of refugee status, the Russian Federation is the country most strongly represented in the case of the withdrawal of subsidiary protection status, with 53 notifications of withdrawal. The countries in the 50% selection represented here are Afghanistan, Iraq and Nigeria (BFA, 2023a). (see Table 11: Decisions withdrawing status (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX)

Characteristics of third-country nationals: ordered to leave and returned following an order to leave

The composition of the countries of citizenship of third-country nationals who have received or are following an order to return has already been described in in this and the previous section. In the following the composition of these groups in terms of sex and age is described.

Between 2018 and 2022 third-country nationals ordered to leave and who returned following an order to leave, were predominantly male and between 18 and 34 years old. Among third-country nationals ordered to leave it is interesting that while the number of males in this age category and of males of 35 years or over strongly increased 2022, the age composition and numbers of females remained stable (compared to 2021). (see Figure 16: Characteristics of Third-country nationals ordered to leave: sex & age, unknown always 0 (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX)

Male third-country nationals between 18 and 34 years make the highest share among third-country nationals ordered to leave between 2018 and 2022, followed by males of 35 years or over. Among the female third-country nationals the proportion of different age groups is more balanced. While in 2018 and

⁶⁹ In certain cases, the residence permit depends on the residence permit of a family member, e.g. the spouse, if the spouse has brought the partner to Austria through family reunification.

2019, the age category between 18 and 34 years is still the most strongly represented, albeit with a slight gap to the age group under 18 years and that of 35 years or above. In the following years, the age group of 35 years or over is slightly more strongly represented; in 2022, both age groups (from 18 to 34 years: 520; and 35 years or above: 515) are almost at the same level. The proportion of female third-country nationals ordered to return has fallen over the years; while in 2018 and 2019 it was still just over 20% of all third-country nationals ordered to leave, in the following years their share fell to 15% (2020) and 14% (2021) and in 2022 even to 6%. With regard to sex and age of third-country nationals returned to a third-country, following an order to leave, it can also be seen here that men aged between 18 and 34 make up the largest proportion, and the group of men aged 35 and over is also strongly represented. Among women, the proportion of those aged 35 and over is the highest in all years. It is also interesting to note that the percentage of women returned following an order to leave is consistently between 25% (minimum 2019) and 28% (2022) (see Figure 17: Characteristics of third-country nationals returned to a third-country, following an order to leave: sex & age (EUROSTAT) Data on the age category less than 18 years is missing for the year 2020 and was coded 0 for further analysis in the ANNEX). About the ratio between men and women ordered to leave, they therefore make up a much higher proportion of third-country nationals returned following an order to leave than the data on third-country nationals ordered to leave would suggest. Gender-specific aspects are also noticeable in the analysis of the types of return, which are discussed below.

Types of return

Voluntary and forced returns have been a central Austrian policy focus in recent years. Migrants can generally participate in voluntary return programmes regardless of how long they have been regularly or irregularly present in the country. Although it is only a small number of irregularly resident persons who approach the BBU without prior contact with the authorities, in order to receive support for voluntary return⁷⁰. In these cases, the personal data is recorded, and support is offered. However, as these are staying irregularly the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA) is informed and checks whether no international investigations or anything else is open. If the voluntary return is approved, the persons are supported in their departure. Increasingly this occurred during the Covid-19 pandemic, presumably due to the uncertainty whether it will even be possible to return to their home country. This means a one-off voluntary assisted departure is granted. In the event of a repeated application, the procedural constellation will be examined (Expert interview 05 on the process leading to and following a return decision with a representative of Department Return, Reintegration and Quality Development of the Federal Ministry of the Interior, March 2024).

The measures for the support of voluntary return are based on a 4-pillar model, consisting of information tools, return counselling, return assistance and reintegration offers (Ministry of Interior, n.d.-a).

⁷⁰ No valid statistical data is available on the exact number of irregularly resident migrants who approach the BBU.

Figure 6: TCNs who have left the territory by type of return (EUROSTAT⁷¹, data available since 2017)

With the exception of 2018, in which a peak of forced returns was recorded (4,925, 66% of the total) and at the same time voluntary returns fell from 73% of total returns in 2017 to 34% - it is also the only year in this period in which forced returns exceeded voluntary returns - data shows that the proportion of voluntary returns has risen steadily since 2019, from 65% (2019) to 79% in 2021. The peculiarities mentioned in 2018 have to be seen in the context of various legal changes, especially the Aliens Amendment Act 2017 (“Fremdenänderungsgesetz”), and the political focus on return measures, particularly concerning rejected asylum seekers. The legal changes and political measures of the post-2015 episode were described in detail in Section 1. The developments in voluntary and forced returns are also partly reflected in the data for the 50% selection of countries of citizenship according to orders to return, meaning that in most cases the share of voluntary returns increased after 2018 and forced returns decreased. For some countries, voluntary returns predominated in 2018, i.e. at a time when forced returns peaked, including Algeria, Morocco, and Nigeria, while forced returns were higher in 2019. From 2020, however, voluntary returns predominate in these countries too. In the case of Iraq, Albania, Serbia, Turkey, Egypt, Tunisia, India, Pakistan and Iraq, voluntary returns outweigh forced returns from 2019 onwards; in the case of Iraq, it is a massive increase compared to previous years. (see Figure 18: Third-country nationals who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship (50% selection) (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX)

The following figure, limited to the period from 2021 until the third quarter of 2023 due to the availability of data (EUROSTAT⁷²), includes non-assisted voluntary returns in addition to the number of third-country nationals returned to a third-country following an order to leave by assisted voluntary return and assisted forced return for the 50 percent selection of countries of citizenship⁷³. On the one hand, the data shows that in all years more than twice as many third-country nationals returned to a third-country by assisted voluntary return than by forced return. In addition, the importance of non-assisted voluntary returns is emphasized, which also exceed assisted voluntary returns in 2022 and up to the third half of 2023.

⁷¹ TCNs who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/MIGR_EIRT_VOL_custom_11826435/default/table?lang=en

⁷² TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex – quarterly data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1_custom_8547137/default/table

⁷³ Including Albania, Serbia, Türkiye, Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, Nigeria, Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Iraq.

Figure 7: Third-country nationals returned to a third-country, following an order to leave, by type of return (50 percent selection) (EUROSTAT⁷⁴)

Data shows, that the majority of third-country nationals return to their country of citizenship (see **Error! Reference source not found.** in the ANNEX), but the type of return differs (See Figure 19: Third-country nationals returned to the country of citizenship or an other third-country, following an order to leave, by sex and type of return (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX). The proportion of assisted forced returns is significantly lower among female third-country nationals in all years compared to those among male third-country nationals, while assisted and non-assisted voluntary returns clearly predominate. Even though forced return is also in third place among male third-country nationals, it is more strongly represented in relation to the other types of return than among female third-country nationals.

Figure 8: Third-country nationals returned to a third-country following an order to leave, by type of return and sex (all countries included) (EUROSTAT⁷⁵)

With regard to the development of the composition of the types of return in this period, the data show for the time being (it must be taken into account that only one half of the year can be included for 2023 and the final data is pending) that while voluntary return to the country of citizenship was by far the most

⁷⁴ TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex – quarterly data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1_custom_8547137/default/table

⁷⁵ TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex – quarterly data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1_custom_7982191/default/table

common variant in 2021, followed by assisted focussed return and non-assisted voluntary return, the figures for non-assisted voluntary return increase significantly in 2022 and account for more than twice as much as forced returns. In 2023, the previous trend shows a similar picture. When returning to another third-country, non-assisted voluntary return is the most important, followed by assisted voluntary return and, in comparatively small numbers, forced returns⁷⁶.

⁷⁶ See Figure 20: Type of return by country of destination: country of citizenship or other third-country (EUROSTAT) in the ANNEX.

SECTION 3: Data production and data loss

In this section of the report findings from the MIrreM project and the implemented workshops and interviews will be addressed through secondary analysis of the data collected in that project and supplemented by one expert interview (synergies Section 1). The MIrreM workshops and interviews addressed issues such as data production, data gaps, data usage, data needs as well as ethical dimensions and concerns. One relevant outcome which can already be mentioned, is that third sector organisations do collect data on irregular migrants, if they are amongst their clients but the actual residence status is usually not documented, partly because the provision of services is independent from the residence status, or because of funding mechanism, ethical concerns and possible risks for their clients (detention, deportation).

National Asylum, apprehension and enforcement statistics

In Austria quantitative data on asylum, irregular migration and return is mainly collected on the federal level and the responsible authorities and usually reports of NGOs, expert opinions, media and academic publications refer to these numbers. This has various reasons: It is publicly available, reliable, and valid administrative data, but quite often published with a limited amount of background information on the (definition of) categories, counting and limitations of the provided data.

The qualitative assessment of available data on irregular migration, indicators and context information illustrated that quite detailed data on various indicators, especially in the context of asylum, is available. National numbers differ from EUROSTAT data due to different definitions of categories as well as in the counting (e.g. counting issued return decisions (EUROSTAT) or legally enforceable return decisions (national data)), therefore comparability is not given. Furthermore, national data is mainly provided in the form of online reports in pdf-format, which complicates the further use for detailed analysis. Also available estimates of the stock of irregularly residing migrants in Austria is based on administrative data: the statistics on crime suspects (Bundeskriminalamt, n.d.). Data on subnational level is mainly collected by the provinces for administrative purposes. Interviewed experts as well as workshop participants of the MIrreM project from third-sector organisations and governmental institutions reported on the dependency and necessary cooperation with the responsible federal state authorities and subcontracted organisations (such as the Austrian Integration Fund) to obtain needed data, e.g. for planning measures, services, and budgets (Expert workshop 01, 05/2023). Even though there is a lack of precise data on the irregular migrant population in Austria, irregular migrants leave traces in various data sets (Jandl, 2009). In Austria, this is mainly administrative data, which is usually published by the various responsible state authorities in the form of publicly accessible reports and presents relevant indicators and provides contextual information. Below is a description of the most relevant data sets at national level and their limitations. Generally critical points that prevent further use of the data for e.g. estimates include the fact that data is published in combined form (e.g. inland and border apprehensions) and that they often do not refer to persons, but for example to apprehensions.

In the Austrian case **three distinct databases** are relevant⁷⁷:

- **Asylum statistics** (applications, open procedures, decisions, resettlement, subsidiary protection, other decisions, unaccompanied minors, minors in general; return decisions following an asylum case, withdrawal of international protection);
- **Apprehension statistics** (covering irregular entries and stays, smuggled persons, smugglers and victims of trafficking);
- **Enforcement statistics** (forced and voluntary returns, expulsion orders, toleration, humanitarian stay, non-refoulement, status withdrawal).

All data sets are based on **person-specific entries** with links to a case or cases. There is **no linkage** between apprehensions, asylum and enforcement statistics databases:

- There is no anonymised unique personal identifier for apprehension statistics and older data is regularly cleaned of personal information (names, etc.) for data protection reasons. It is in principle to match apprehension data with other databases (asylum, residence permits, enforcement data), but only by using names, date of birth and other identifiers.
- It is unclear whether anonymous unique identifiers exist for asylum and enforcement related data. So far, administrative migration related datasets are not included in the statistical ecosystem of the Austrian Microdata Centre operated by Statistics Austria.
- Personal data is deleted after a certain period after last modification; personal data of recognised refugees is deleted as well, latest upon acquisition of a long-term residence or citizenship. The law enforcement database is linkable to other datasets (e.g. population register, residence permit database) and information on current or most recent permits (residence permit database) or residence status (Residence Register) is accessible to the Ministry of the Interior, but the databases do not store historical information.

➔ Given the limitations of the current system of databases, there it is not possible to systematically trace people through different databases.

In Austria the Ministry of Interior publishes data on asylum applications, including the numbers and related variables such as country of citizenship, age, sex, of asylum applicants, asylum decisions (differing between first and second instance) and developments of foreigners in basic care, yearly since 2002 and monthly for the current year. Several topics, such as the numbers of foreigners in basic care and characteristics of asylum applicants were only included relatively recently. Furthermore, information included in between in the reports, such as on Dublin-processes, voluntary and forced return and decisions on humanitarian status, were excluded through the implementation of the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA) from 2014 onwards and mainly can be found later on in the reports published by the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum.⁷⁸ Although the Ministry of Interior provides the Statistic Austria with national data for further processing for EUROSTAT, and therefore EUROSTAT and national reports provide data from the identical data source (the system of Integrated Foreign Administration (IFA – 'Integrierte

⁷⁷ No statistical databases or interactive interfaces are available to the public and only limited statistics relating to managed migration are accessible via statistics Austria website. Statistics are available from the Ministry of the Interior website (<https://www.bmi.gv.at/Downloads/start.aspx>) as downloads in pdf format. The Eurostat database generally offers a more user-friendly access.

⁷⁸ More detailed information on changes of data processing and the national data management in the year 2014 can be found in Section 3.

Fremdenadministration`), the national reports on the asylum statistic emphasize that a direct comparison of the national data with the Eurostat data is only possible to a limited extent due to different definitions, the reliance on legally binding decisions in national statistics as opposed to Eurostat's person-focused and non-decision-related counting method (see BMI 2022). While differences between certain data is thus well explainable, such as person related countings of asylum applicants (EUROSTAT) and of asylum applications (national), others are more tricky, like the different numbers on decisions on humanitarian status, which are caused by the definition of the category and the inclusion as well as exclusion of decisions based on the e.g. pathway (ex officio or by individual application) or the interlinkage to an asylum application. While EUROSTAT⁷⁹ only includes data on positive decisions on humanitarian status interlinked with an application for asylum, the asylum statistics reports of the Ministry of Interior⁸⁰ provide an additional differentiation between legally valid (another already mentioned difference between the national and EUROSTAT data on asylum) positive and negative decisions on residence permits for exceptional circumstances for foreigners with and without asylum application.

Regarding irregular flows, the Federal Criminal Police Office produced situation reports on migrant smuggling and trafficking in human beings available online on an annual basis. In the report 2022, a basic distinction is made between "smuggled persons" and "persons who have entered or are staying unlawfully". The second category includes foreigners who have been found to be present within the country's territory after crossing the national border without the assistance of a smuggler and without possessing the necessary documents. It also includes individuals who have been denied entry at the border or who have been issued an entry or residency ban. Additionally, it encompasses persons who were granted entry but have since become subject to deportation due to their illegal stay. Furthermore, it includes individuals who were employed in Austria without possessing the appropriate residence permit and those who have been apprehended or attempted to enter the country in defiance of an existing entry or residency ban (BMI II / Bundeskriminalamt, 2023).

The data reflect the apprehensions of persons according to these two categories (a third category is smugglers) and differentiate between age group, nationality, gender, and place of apprehension (province and district). The aggregation of the above-mentioned subgroups of persons under the category "persons who have entered or are staying unlawfully" is questionable, since apprehension figures do not allow to distinguish between apprehensions of persons with longer residence in Austria - and border apprehensions, while also counting repeat apprehensions of the same persons if not attributed to the same case.

The role of third sector organisations: Data gaps and loss

Third sector organisations, such as NGOs are mostly dependent on a combination of municipal and federal funding, as well as donations, and operate in a field of economic, legal and social tension in their work (Hombberger, Kirchhoff, Mallet, et al., 2022). In general, it can be said that funding of third sector organisations in the field of migration and integration is often interlinked with defined target groups (such as asylum seekers, migrants with an international protection status or with a high probability of remaining) and an obligation to document and report certain characteristics of participants, including their residence status, in order to be able to check whether the target group has been reached. If measures concerning the target groups are set up so broadly that they also allow access to irregularly resident migrants, the residence status is generally not documented. It is partly due to the interplay of these funding mechanisms that third sector organisations do not collect (quantitative and / or qualitative) data on the number and characteristics of irregularly resident migrants, even if they are among their clients. And even if they do, this data is not shared for ethical reasons and is only used for the planning and orientation of internal

⁷⁹ First instance decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfst_custom_12119270/default/table?lang=en

⁸⁰ Asylum reports/ statistics by the Ministry of Interior: <https://www.bmi.gv.at/301/Statistiken/>

measures. In the MIrreM workshop on data on irregular migration in Austria: needs, use and challenges, various stakeholders also pointed out that it is the NGOs that are in contact and exchange with the irregular population and also have the corresponding data (Expert workshop 01, 05/2023).

In order to counteract this loss of data or to close the data gap on (characteristics of) irregular migrants, the question arises whether and how it could be made possible for NGOs to share their data on irregular migrants or make it accessible without having to fear repercussions for their organisation or their clientele (e.g. in the form of an anonymized database in which third sector organisations can enter data).

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ANNEX

Table 3: Overview of relevant legislative changes between 2009 and 2022

Title of policy/law	Year	Web link to source
Amendment to the "Right to Remain" ("Bleiberechtsnovelle")	2009	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2009_I_29/BGBLA_2009_I_29.pdf
Act amending the Law on Aliens ("Fremdenrechtsänderungsgesetz")	2009	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2009_I_122/BGBLA_2009_I_122.pdf
Aliens' Authorities Restructuring Act (amendments 2013 and 2014) („Fremdenbehördenneustrukturierungsgesetz“)	2012	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2012_I_87/BGBLA_2012_I_87.pdf
Act amending the Law on Aliens ("Fremdenrechtsänderungsgesetz")	2015	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2015_I_70/BGBLA_2015_I_70.pdf
Act amending the Law on Aliens ("Fremdenrechtsänderungsgesetz")	2017	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2017_I_84/BGBLA_2017_I_84.pdf
Basic Act on Social Assistance ("Sozialhilfe-Grundsatzgesetz")	2019	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2019_I_41/BGBLA_2019_I_41.pdf

Table 4: Overview of the most relevant categories of migrants in an irregular situation in Austria and possible implications, such as administrative penalties, entry bans and deportation

Migrants in an irregular situation	Description: definition, possible consequences
Over-stayers (third-country national)	<p>Third-country nationals who lawfully entered Austria (with valid travel documents and (if needed) visas) but stayed beyond time limits or conditions of the entry title or the visa-free stay or the determined duration of stay.</p> <p>Administrative offence: -) fine according fine of unlawful residence: 500 up to 2,500€ or imprisonment for up to two weeks. In case of an already existing conviction of an illegal stay, fines amount from 2,500 to 7,500€ or imprisonment for up to four weeks (Aliens Police Act §120); -) deportation (Aliens Police Act § 46); -) entry ban (Aliens Police Act § 53)</p>
Rejected asylum seekers and persons who have applied for subsidiary protection	<p>A person covered by a first instance decision rejecting an application for international protection, (including decisions considering applications as inadmissible or unfounded, decisions under priority and accelerated procedures). A complaint can be filed with the Federal Administrative Court Austria within 14 days. The BFA can issue a return decision, which must be complied with within the defined deadline. If there is no voluntary return, forced return can be implemented (Aliens Police Act § 46) and an entry ban might be issued (Aliens Police Act § 53).</p>
Persons who have crossed the Austrian border unlawfully and have not applied for international protection	<p>A person who has entered Austrian territory unlawfully (without the mandatory travel documents and visa) commits an administrative offense. -) fine of 100 to 1,000€ or by imprisonment for up to two weeks. A person who has already been legally punished for illegal entry is liable to a fine of 1,000 to 5,000€ or to imprisonment for up to three weeks (Aliens Police Act §120). -) deportation (Aliens Police Act § 46); -) entry ban (Aliens Police Act § 53)</p> <p>Any foreigner, who does not reside lawfully in the territory of Austria (without a valid visa or resident permit) commits an administrative offense. -) fine of 500 up to 2,500€ or imprisonment for up to two weeks. In case of an already existing conviction of an illegal stay, fines amount from 2,500 to 7,500€ or imprisonment for up to four weeks. (Aliens Police Act §120); -) deportation (Aliens Police Act § 46); -) entry ban (Aliens Police Act § 53)</p>

Third-country nationals with entry or residence ban.	Third-country nationals, who have entered or remained in Austria despite a ban on entry or residence. Administrative offence, liable to a fine of 5,000 to 15,000€ or to imprisonment for up to six weeks (Aliens Police Act §120); -) deportation (Aliens Police Act § 46)
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Table 5: Governmental authorities and responsibilities

Gov. authorities	Web link
Ministry of Interior ("Bundesministerium für Inneres" - BMI)	https://www.bmi.gv.at/102/start.aspx
Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum ("Bundesamt für Fremdenwesen und Asyl" - BFA)/Ministry of Interior	www.bfa.gv.at
Federal Criminal Police Office (Bundeskriminalamt (BK))/Ministry of Interior	https://www.bundeskriminalamt.at/101/start.aspx
Federal Agency for Reception and Support Services (Bundesagentur für Betreuungs- und Unterstützungsleistungen (BBU))/ Ministry of Interior	https://www.bbu.gv.at/en
Joint Coordination Platform (JCP) (Koordinationszentrum für Migration/ Ministry of Interior)	https://bmi.gv.at/113/Sektion_V/Joint_Coordination_Plattform/start.aspx https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVII/AB/5622/imfname_953538.pdf
Finance Police ("Finanzpolizei"/ Federal Ministry of Finance)	https://www.bmf.gv.at/themen/betrugsbekaempfung/einheiten-betrugsbekaempfung/amt-fuer-betrugsbekaempfung/finanzpolizei.html
Aliens Police (Fremdenpolizei)/ Ministry of Interior	https://www.polizei.gv.at/wien/lpd/organigramm/organigramm_afa.aspx https://www.bmi.gv.at/202/Fremdenpolizei_und_Grenzkontrolle/ https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/NormDokument.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=20004241&Paragraf=2
Federal Administrative Court Austria (Bundesverwaltungsgericht Österreich)	https://www.bvwg.gv.at/fachbereiche/fremdenwesen_asy_l_neu_start.html

Table 6: Bilateral agreements linked to readmission since 2010

Agreement (IRF)	Date of Entry Into Force	Web Link
<p>Agreement between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Republic of Kosovo on the Admission and Transit of Persons</p>	<p>01.03.2011</p>	<p>Agreement (in German): https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2011_III_21/COO_2026_100_2_652966.pdfsig</p> <p>Implementation protocol (German version): https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2011_III_21/COO_2026_100_2_652967.pdfsig</p>
<p>Agreement on Readmission between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria</p>	<p>18.08.2012</p>	<p>Federal Law Gazette: https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2012_III_116/BGBLA_2012_III_116.pdfsig</p> <p>Agreement (English version): https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2012_III_116/COO_2026_100_2_778706.pdfsig</p>
<p>Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Council of Ministers of Bosnia and Herzegovina for the Implementation of the Agreement between the European Community and Bosnia and Herzegovina on the readmission of persons residing without authorisation</p>	<p>20.02.2012</p>	<p>Protocol (English version): https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2012_III_50/COO_2026_100_2_734079.html</p>
<p>2011 Implementing Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Russian Federation on the implementation of the Agreement between the Russian Federation and the European Community on readmission of</p>	<p>03.06.2011</p>	<p>Federal Law Gazette: https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2011_III_140/BGBLA_2011_III_140.pdfsig</p> <p>Implementation protocol (German version): https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2011_III_140/COO_2026_100_2_701446.pdfsig</p>
<p>Implementing Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on the implementation of the Agreement between the European Community and Ukraine on the readmission of persons.</p>	<p>20.11.2014</p>	<p>Implementation protocol (in German): https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2015_III_9/COO_2026_100_2_1068382.pdfsig</p>
<p>Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of Georgia on the Implementation of the Agreement between the European Union and Georgia on the Readmission of Persons Residing Without Authorisation</p>	<p>01.01.2014</p>	<p>Protocol (English version): https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2013_III_318/COO_2026_100_2_941890.html</p>

<p>Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Republic of Moldova on the implementation of the Agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Moldova on the readmission of persons residing without authorization</p>	<p>26.11.2010</p>	<p>Corrigendum to the proclamation of the Federal Chancellor concerning the Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Government of the Republic of Moldova on the implementation of the Agreement between the European Community and the Republic of Moldova on the the readmission of persons residing without authorization</p> <p>https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2011_III_124/BGBLA_2011_III_124.pdfsig</p> <p>Protocol (English version):</p> <p>https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2010_III_128/COO_2026_100_2_625125.pdfsig</p>
<p>Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Republic of Serbia on the implementation of the agreement between the European Community and the and the Republic of Serbia on the readmission of persons residing without authorization</p>	<p>18.04.2011</p>	<p>Protocol (English version):</p> <p>https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2010_III_128/COO_2026_100_2_625125.pdfsig</p>
<p>Joint Declaration between the Kingdom of Morocco and the Republic of Austria</p>	<p>not specified</p>	<p>Joint declaration (English version):</p> <p>https://www.bmeia.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Vertretungen/Rabat/Declaration_MA-AT.pdf</p>
<p>Agreement between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Republic of India on a Comprehensive Migration and Mobility Partnership</p>	<p>09.01.2023</p>	<p>Agreement (English version):</p> <p>https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2023_III_127/Anlagen_0002_5_A165961_9748_402A_A394_31D68B742BBB.pdfsig</p>
<p>Protocol on the implementation of the Agreement on the readmission of persons residing without authorization, as published in the Official Journal of European Union, L 334/1 – L 334/24 on 19.12.2007, concluded between the Government of the Republic of Austria represented by the Federal Minister of the Interior and the Government of the Republic of Macedonia</p>	<p>not specified</p>	<p>Implementation protocol (English version):</p> <p>https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2011_III_146/COO_2026_100_2_703606.pFdfsig</p>
<p>Protocol between the Austrian Federal Government and the Government of the Republic of Armenia on the implementation of the Agreement between the European Union and the Republic of Armenia on the readmission of persons residing without authorization</p>	<p>01.05.2024</p>	<p>no link available (checked on 19/02/2024)</p>

<p>Memorandum of Understanding on police cooperation between Austria and Iraq: As part of a working visit by Foreign Minister Alexander Schallenberg to Baghdad, Federal Police Director Michael Takács signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on September 11, 2023.</p>	<p>not available</p>	<p>No web link to the MoU available, but to a report of the BMEIA (accessed 19/02/2024) (German version): https://www.bmi.gv.at/news.aspx?id=582B5A71616B71577341343D</p>
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Source: based on <https://www.jeanpierrecassarino.com/datasets/ra/autriche/> Governments' official bulletins and internal documents. J.-P. Cassarino ©, supplemented by recent agreements (2023, if not already included) and web links, translation by the authors.

Note: Among the listed documents are seven on the implementation of the agreement between the European Union and Bosnia and Herzegovina/ Georgia/ Russian Federation/ Ukraine/ Macedonia/ Serbia/ Moldova. These documents are only supplementary to EURAs, so the information they contain is limited and only refers to the implementing protocols.

Table 7: Top twenty countries of citizenship of third-country nationals who have left the territory of Austria to a third-country (country of citizenship or other third-country) and of third-country nationals ordered to leave between 2017 and 2022 (EUROSTAT⁸¹). The return rate calculated by the *provided tool of the EU return dashboard*⁸². The return rate refers to the aforementioned country in the column for third-country nationals ordered to leave.

	2017				2018				2019				2020				2021				2022									
	TCNs left to a TC	TCNs OTL	RR		TCNs left to a TC	TCNs OTL	RR		TCNs left to a TC	TCNs OTL	RR		TCNs left to a TC	TCNs OTL	RR		TCNs left to a TC	TCNs OTL	RR		TCNs left to a TC	TCNs OTL	RR							
1	RS	983	AF	1 315	25%	RS	1 259	AF	2 745	13%	RS	1 445	AF	3 765	11%	RS	1 113	AF	1 540	8%	RS	1 135	MA	1 210	1%	RS	1 010	TN	6 410	1%
2	IQ	684	RS	845	100%	IQ	633	RS	1 100	100%	AL	435	RS	1 320	100%	GE	388	RS	1 260	88%	AL	390	RS	1 125	100%	AL	410	IN	4 415	5%
3	UA	431	IQ	815	84%	GE	525	NG	765	35%	GE	426	IQ	1 235	26%	AL	343	IQ	665	14%	RU	240	AF	870	13%	GE	400	PK	4 005	1%
4	AF	334	PK	760	14%	RU	468	IQ	735	86%	AF	401	NG	650	48%	UA	282	MA	465	4%	UA	225	PK	720	7%	TR	270	MA	3 385	1%
5	RU	333	NG	485	38%	AF	367	GE	535	98%	UA	387	GE	625	68%	BA	257	TR	360	67%	GE	205	IQ	665	23%	CN*	255	RS	875	100%
6	GE	274	DZ	385	48%	AL	314	RU	465	100%	NG	317	RU	520	55%	CN*	255	AL	355	97%	CN*	190	EG	600	8%	BA	225	EG	680	9%
7	AL	179	IN	345	25%	UA	313	PK	440	27%	IQ	313	UA	510	75%	TR	239	RU	355	51%	BA	185	BD	545	6%	IN	225	BD	455	4%
8	XK*	256	MA	310	37%	NG	269	IN	350	40%	CN*	300	SO	440	1%	MK	206	GE	355	100%	TR	185	IN	490	15%	MK	220	TR	415	65%
9	MK	254	UA	305	100%	CN*	258	SO	340	0%	MK	292	AL	425	100%	RU	182	NG	335	40%	NG	155	RU	405	59%	MD	165	DZ	385	10%
10	CN*	188	RU	300	100%	MK	240	UA	315	100%	RU	284	IN	375	41%	NG	137	IN	305	25%	IQ	155	AL	370	100%	NG	140	GE	355	100%
11	DZ	186	SO	285	2%	BA	235	AL	225	100%	BA	283	PK	360	26%	XK*	127	IR	280	13%	MK	150	NG	305	51%	RU	140	IQ	350	34%
12	NG	184	GE	235	100%	TR	203	MK	210	100%	TR	276	TR	320	86%	AF	123	UA	265	100%	XK*	135	TR	285	65%	XK*	130	MD	300	55%
13	BA	170	MK	205	100%	XK*	189	DZ	205	66%	XK*	209	IR	300	25%	IQ	92	BA	245	100%	MD	125	DZ	275	2%	IQ	120	AL	285	100%
14	IR	155	XK*	195	100%	AM	159	BA	190	100%	IN	154	BA	285	100%	MD	86	BD	240	4%	AF	110	GE	245	84%	IR	105	NG	260	54%
15	MA	117	AL	180	100%	IN	140	MA	190	50%	MD	101	MK	245	100%	IN	74	PK	235	21%	AM	80	TN	240	10%	AM	90	RU	255	55%
16	AM	112	SY	175	37%	DZ	134	AM	180	89%	AM	98	SY	240	25%	AM	64	MK	225	91%	IN	75	IR	230	20%	US	85	UA	225	9%
17	PK	106	BA	170	100%	PK	121	IR	170	47%	PK	93	CN*	205	100%	ME	54	DZ	195	8%	US	55	UA	230	98%	PH	65	BA	210	100%
18	TR	105	CN*	155	100%	SY	121	CN*	160	100%	DZ	89	MA	180	31%	EG	51	XK*	175	71%	PK	50	BA	205	90%	UZ	65	IR	195	54%
19	IN	83	AM	150	73%	MA	95	TR	150	100%	IR	74	AM	180	56%	PK	50	EG	155	32%	EG	45	AM	155	52%	JO	60	MK	185	100%
20	SY	65	TR	120	88%	MD	79	XK*	145	100%	MN	62	BD	170	12%	MN	40	CN*	145	100%	IR	45	MK	155	97%	EG	60	XK*	120	100%

*China (CN) inclusive Hongkong

*Kosovo (XK) under United Nations Security Council Resolution 1244/99

To enable the comprehensive presentation in the table, the country codes according to the ISO-3166-1 alpha 2 coding list were used: RS - Serbia; AF - Afghanistan; IQ - Iraq; UA - Ukraine; RU - Russia; GE - Georgia; AL - Albania; XK - Kosovo; MK - North Macedonia; CN - China; DZ - Algeria; SY - Syria; IN - India; TR - Türkiye; PK - Pakistan; AM - Armenia; MA - Morocco; IR - Iran; BA - Bosnia and Herzegovina; NG - Nigeria; SO - Somalia; JO - Jordan; US - United States; MD - Moldova; UZ - Uzbekistan; PH - Philippines; BD - Bangladesh; TN - Tunisia; EG - Egypt.

⁸¹ TCNs who have left Austria to a third-country (country of citizenship or other third-country):

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_des_custom_12116975/default/table?lang=en

TCNs ordered to leave: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord_custom_8452554/default/table

⁸² Return rate calculated by: <https://migration-demography-tools.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dashboards/eu-migration-return-msc-and-sacs-perspective>

Table 8: Third-country nationals who have left the territory to a third-country by type of agreement procedure and citizenship (total and 50% selection)⁸³ (EUROSTAT⁸⁴)

	2018				2019			
	Returned under EU Readmission Agreement (EURA)	Returned under other readmission agreement	Returned without existing a readmission agreement	Unknown	Returned under EU Readmission Agreement (EURA)	Returned under other readmission agreement	Returned without existing a readmission agreement	Unknown
Albania	314	0	0	0	435	0	0	0
Serbia	1 259	0	0	0	1 445	0	0	0
Türkiye	203	0	0	0	276	0	0	0
Algeria	0	0	0	134	0	0	0	89
Egypt	0	0	0	55	0	0	0	57
Morocco	0	0	0	95	0	0	0	55
Tunisia	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	42
Nigeria	0	269	0	0	0	317	0	0
Afghanistan	0	367	0	0	0	401	0	0
Bangladesh	0	29	0	0	0	21	0	0
India	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	154
Pakistan	121	0	0	0	93	0	0	0
Iraq	0	0	0	633	0	0	313	0
Total	3 978	719	0	2 108	4 202	772	694	1 132

⁸³ 2017 was excluded since all existing numbers fall under the category "Unknown".

⁸⁴ Third-country nationals who have left the territory to a third-country by type of agreement procedure and citizenship:
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_agr_custom_8546344/default/table

	2020				2021			
	Returned under EU Readmission Agreement (EURA)	Returned under other readmission agreement	Returned without existing a readmission agreement	Unknown	Returned under EU Readmission Agreement (EURA)	Returned under other readmission agreement	Returned without existing a readmission agreement	Unknown
Albania	343	0	0	0	390	0	0	0
Serbia	1 113	0	0	0	1 135	0	0	0
Türkiye	239	0	0	0	185	0	0	0
Algeria	0	0	10	6	0	0	5	0
Egypt	0	0	45	6	0	0	45	0
Morocco	0	0	15	5	0	0	5	5
Tunisia	0	0	13	2	0	0	25	0
Nigeria	0	137	0	0	0	0	90	65
Afghanistan	0	123	0	0	0	110	0	0
Bangladesh	0	10	0	0	0	35	0	0
India	0	0	68	6	0	0	55	15
Pakistan	50	0	0	0	50	0	0	0
Iraq	0	0	92	0	0	0	155	0
Total	3 285	281	993	40	3 075	150	1 160	95

Table 9: Overview of first time asylum applicants, first instance positive decisions and rejected asylum applications, third-country nationals ordered to leave, third-country nationals returned to a third-country following an order to leave and of the return rate between 2016 and 2022 (50 percent selection of countries of citizenship acc. OTL) (EUROSTAT⁸⁵)

		2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Albania	Asylum applicants*	75	40	55	50	15	35	35
	Pos. decisions (total)	5	15	0	10	10	0	0
	Rejected	135	50	70	45	25	30	20
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	145	180	315	435	345	390	410
	TCNs OTL	285	180	225	425	355	370	285
	RR	51%	100%	100%	100%	97%	100%	100%
Serbia	Asylum applicants*	160	125	105	40	40	55	45
	Pos. decisions (total)	15	25	10	20	40	15	10
	Rejected	225	150	125	75	35	55	35
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	685	985	1260	1445	1115	1135	1010
	TCNs OTL	1715	845	1100	1320	1260	1125	875
	RR	40%	100%	100%	100%	88%	100%	100%
Türkiye	Asylum applicants*	310	260	175	245	280	875	5240
	Pos. decisions (total)	30	40	100	90	100	185	100
	Rejected	80	180	185	235	145	145	270
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	75	105	205	275	240	185	270
	TCNs OTL	225	120	150	320	360	285	415
	RR	33%	88%	100%	86%	67%	65%	65%
Algeria	Asylum applicants*	850	220	80	120	325	425	580
	Pos. decisions (total)	5	5	5	0	5	0	5
	Rejected	865	380	150	110	180	240	345
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	60	185	135	90	15	5	40
	TCNs OTL	775	385	205	155	195	275	385
	RR	8%	48%	66%	58%	8%	2%	10%
Egypt	Asylum applicants*	200	130	85	45	165	955	1550
	Pos. decisions (total)	55	40	20	20	10	10	10
	Rejected	95	105	135	85	110	640	500
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	20	25	55	55	50	45	60
	TCNs OTL	85	100	115	100	155	600	680
	RR	24%	25%	48%	55%	32%	8%	9%
Morocco	Asylum applicants*	935	205	90	110	705	1850	8625
	Pos. decisions (total)	10	5	5	10	5	5	10
	Rejected	965	295	140	105	450	1280	3675
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	50	115	95	55	20	15	50
	TCNs OTL	895	310	190	180	465	1210	3385
	RR	6%	37%	50%	31%	4%	1%	1%
Tunisia	Asylum applicants*	125	70	35	55	145	500	13060
	Pos. decisions (total)	5	0	10	0	0	5	5
	Rejected	125	70	40	40	55	270	6395
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	20	50	35	40	15	25	45
	TCNs OTL	120	85	70	70	60	240	6410
	RR	17%	59%	50%	57%	25%	10%	1%
Nigeria	Asylum applicants*	1645	1135	395	170	100	90	125
	Pos. decisions (total)	50	45	50	50	40	40	35
	Rejected	520	980	720	300	140	100	95
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	90	185	270	315	135	155	140
	TCNs OTL	440	485	765	650	335	305	260
	RR	20%	38%	35%	48%	40%	51%	54%

Table continues next page.

⁸⁵ Asylum applicants by type, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asyappctza_custom_8527230/default/table

First instance decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfsta_custom_8527009/default/table

Third-country nationals returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex – quarterly data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1_custom_8547137/default/table

TCNs ordered to leave - annual data (rounded):

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord_custom_8452554/default/table

RR calculated by <https://migration-demography-tools.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dashboards/eu-migration-return-msc-and-sacs-perspective>

Afghanistan	Asylum applicants*	11520	3525	1765	2585	2825	8050	24445
	Pos. decisions (total)	3870	5900	4340	1735	1350	1515	2260
	Rejected	3165	8650	8255	1310	610	465	155
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	600	335	365	400	125	110	15
	TCNs OTL	430	1315	2745	3765	1540	870	70
	RR	100%	25%	13%	11%	8%	13%	21%
Bangladesh	Asylum applicants*	290	125	95	205	215	980	1085
	Pos. decisions (total)	50	40	45	30	10	20	15
	Rejected	140	165	185	195	130	520	400
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	10	10	30	20	10	35	20
	TCNs OTL	70	60	70	170	240	545	455
	RR	14%	17%	43%	12%	4%	6%	4%
India	Asylum applicants*	415	310	195	295	140	870	19855
	Pos. decisions (total)	15	5	10	0	0	5	5
	Rejected	325	470	450	300	200	555	4810
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	80	85	140	155	75	75	225
	TCNs OTL	505	345	350	375	305	490	4415
	RR	16%	25%	40%	41%	25%	15%	5%
Pakistan	Asylum applicants*	2415	1445	160	255	145	1315	7900
	Pos. decisions (total)	35	50	50	20	20	20	40
	Rejected	815	1085	555	260	120	725	4005
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	90	105	120	95	50	50	40
	TCNs OTL	735	760	440	360	235	720	4005
	RR	12%	14%	27%	26%	21%	7%	7%
Iraq	Asylum applicants*	2725	1345	650	605	625	955	900
	Pos. decisions (total)	2605	2010	1260	405	300	305	270
	Rejected	625	2740	2705	540	185	240	205
	TCNs returned to a TC, following OTL	1350	685	635	315	90	155	120
	TCNs OTL	255	815	735	1235	665	665	350
	RR	100%	84%	86%	26%	14%	23%	34%

*first time applicants

Figure 9: Third-country nationals ordered to leave (50% selection) (EUROSTAT⁸⁶)

⁸⁶ Third-country nationals ordered to leave - annual data (rounded):

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eiord_custom_8452554/default/table

Figure 10: Third-country nationals returned to a third-country, following an order to leave (50% selection) (EUROSTAT⁸⁷)

Figure 11: Asylum applicants (including first instance applicants and subsequent applicants), first instance decisions on applications: rejections of asylum applications and the total of positive decisions (including positive decisions on a Geneva convention status, subsidiary protection status and humanitarian status) between 2011 and 2022. (EUROSTAT⁸⁸)

⁸⁷ TCNs returned following an order to leave - annual data (rounded):

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn_custom_8457166/default/table

⁸⁸ First instance decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfsta_custom_12119270/default/table?lang=en

Figure 12: Third-country nationals found to be illegally present per country of citizenship (50% selection) between 2010 and 2022. (EUROSTAT⁸⁹)

Figure 13: Third-country nationals refused entry at the external borders by country of citizenship (selection 50%) - annual data (rounded) (EUROSTAT⁹⁰)

⁸⁹ Third-country nationals found to be illegally present - annual data (rounded): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eipre_custom_8514525/default/table

⁹⁰ TCNs refused entry at the external borders - annual data (rounded): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirfs_custom_8514984/default/table

Figure 14: Third-country nationals refused entry at the external borders by reason- annual data (rounded) (EUROSTAT⁹¹)

⁹¹ Third-country nationals refused entry at the external borders - annual data (rounded): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirfs_custom_8514718/default/table

Table 10: First instance decisions on applications by type of decision (50% selection) (EUROSTAT⁹²)

		Albania	Serbia	Türkiye	Algeria	Egypt	Morocco	Tunisia	Nigeria	Afghanistan	Bangladesh	India	Pakistan	Iraq
2016	Total	140	235	110	870	150	970	130	570	7 035	195	335	850	3 235
	Total positive decisions	5	15	30	5	55	10	5	50	3 870	50	15	35	2 605
	Rejected	135	225	80	865	95	965	125	520	3 165	140	325	815	625
	Geneva Convention status	0%	33%	50%	100%	73%	50%	0%	30%	39%	70%	0%	71%	62%
	Humanitarian status	0%	67%	33%	100%	18%	50%	100%	40%	0%	30%	33%	14%	0%
	Subsidiary protection status	0%	0%	17%	0%	0%	0%	0%	30%	60%	10%	67%	29%	38%
2017	Total	60	170	220	380	140	305	75	1 025	14 550	205	475	1 135	4 755
	Total positive decisions	15	25	40	5	40	5	0	45	5 900	40	5	50	2 010
	Rejected	50	150	180	380	105	295	70	980	8 650	165	470	1 085	2 740
	Geneva Convention status	0%	20%	75%	0%	63%	0%	0%	11%	46%	63%	0%	60%	51%
	Humanitarian status	67%	40%	13%	100%	25%	0%	0%	44%	1%	25%	100%	10%	0%
	Subsidiary protection status	0%	20%	13%	0%	0%	100%	0%	44%	53%	0%	0%	30%	49%
2018	Total	70	135	290	155	155	150	50	775	12 595	230	460	610	3 965
	Total positive decisions	0	10	100	5	20	5	10	50	4 340	45	10	50	1 260
	Rejected	70	125	185	150	135	140	40	720	8 255	185	450	555	2 705
	Geneva Convention status	0%	50%	80%	0%	75%	0%	0%	20%	55%	67%	0%	60%	54%
	Humanitarian status	0%	50%	10%	0%	25%	100%	100%	50%	6%	11%	50%	30%	7%
	Subsidiary protection status	0%	0%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	30%	39%	22%	0%	20%	38%
2019	Total	55	95	320	110	105	110	45	350	3 045	220	300	280	950
	Total positive decisions	10	20	90	0	20	10	0	50	1 735	30	0	20	405
	Rejected	45	75	235	110	85	105	40	300	1 310	195	300	260	540
	Geneva Convention status	0%	50%	89%	0%	75%	50%	0%	20%	67%	50%	0%	75%	58%
	Humanitarian status	50%	50%	6%	0%	25%	50%	0%	40%	13%	17%	0%	25%	10%
	Subsidiary protection status	0%	0%	6%	0%	0%	0%	0%	40%	20%	17%	0%	0%	32%
2020	Total	35	55	245	185	120	455	55	180	1 960	140	205	140	490
	Total positive decisions	10	20	100	5	10	5	0	40	1 350	10	0	20	300
	Rejected	25	35	145	180	110	450	55	140	610	130	200	120	185
	Geneva Convention status	0%	0%	95%	0%	50%	0%	0%	13%	65%	100%	0%	75%	48%
	Humanitarian status	100%	100%	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%	63%	13%	0%	0%	25%	13%
	Subsidiary protection status	0%	0%	5%	0%	0%	100%	0%	25%	22%	0%	0%	0%	38%
2021	Total	35	70	330	240	650	1 280	275	140	1 980	540	560	745	545
	Total positive decisions	0	15	185	0	10	5	5	40	1 515	20	5	20	305
	Rejected	30	55	145	240	640	1 280	270	100	465	520	555	725	240
	Geneva Convention status	0%	33%	95%	0%	50%	0%	100%	25%	64%	75%	0%	50%	49%
	Humanitarian status	0%	67%	3%	0%	50%	0%	0%	25%	2%	25%	0%	25%	5%
	Subsidiary protection status	0%	0%	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	38%	34%	0%	0%	0%	46%
2022	Total	25	45	370	350	505	3 685	6 400	125	2 415	415	4 810	4 045	475
	Total positive decisions	0	10	100	5	10	10	5	35	2 260	15	5	40	270
	Rejected	20	35	270	345	500	3 675	6 395	95	155	400	4 810	4 005	205
	Geneva Convention status	0%	50%	85%	100%	50%	50%	0%	0%	55%	100%	0%	75%	44%
	Humanitarian status	0%	50%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	29%	0%	0%	100%	25%	13%
	Subsidiary protection status	0%	0%	5%	0%	0%	0%	0%	57%	44%	0%	0%	0%	41%

⁹² First instance decisions on applications by type of decision, citizenship, age and sex - annual aggregated data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asydcfsta_custom_12117431/default/table?lang=en

Figure 15: Issued toleration cards 2011 until 2022 (2020 January to September 2021 missing value). Source: parliamentary inquiries⁹³

Table 11: Decisions withdrawing status (EUROSTAT⁹⁴)

Decisions withdrawing status granted at first instance decision by type of status withdrawn and reason						
	2021			2022		
	Geneva Convention status	Humanitarian status	Subsidiary protection status	Geneva Convention status	Humanitarian status	Subsidiary protection status
Withdrawn due to revocation	1 450	0	565	1 060	0	225
Withdrawn due to ending	0	0	0	0	0	0
Withdrawn due to refusal to renew	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0
Decisions withdrawing status granted as final decision in appeal or review by type of status withdrawn						
	2021			2022		
	Geneva Convention status	Humanitarian status	Subsidiary protection status	Geneva Convention status	Humanitarian status	Subsidiary protection status
Withdrawn due to revocation	270	0	275	205	0	145
Withdrawn due to ending	0	0	0	0	0	0
Withdrawn due to refusal to renew	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0

⁹³ https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXV/AB/185/fname_339332.pdf, accessed Nov. 2023

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXV/AB/7947/imfname_526034.pdf, accessed Nov. 2023

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVII/AB/3698/imfname_853494.pdf, accessed Nov. 2023

https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVII/AB/13976/imfname_1555646.pdf, accessed Nov. 2023

⁹⁴ Decisions withdrawing status granted at first instance decision by type of status withdrawn, citizenship and reason - annual aggregated data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asywitfsta_custom_12119613/default/table?lang=en

Decisions withdrawing status granted as final decision in appeal or review by type of status withdrawn, citizenship and reason - annual data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_asywitfina_custom_8634472/default/table

Figure 16: Characteristics of Third-country nationals ordered to leave: sex & age, unknown always 0 (EUROSTAT⁹⁵)

Figure 17: Characteristics of third-country nationals returned to a third-country, following an order to leave: sex & age (EUROSTAT⁹⁶) Data on the age category less than 18 years is missing for the year 2020 and was coded 0 for further analysis

⁹⁵ TCNs ordered to leave - annual data (rounded):

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/MIGR_EIORD_custom_7506104/default/table

⁹⁶ TCNs returned following an order to leave - annual data (rounded):

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/MIGR_EIRTN_custom_7509776/default/table

Figure 18: Third-country nationals who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship (50% selection) (EUROSTAT⁹⁷)

Table 12: Third-country nationals who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship (50% selection and total) between 2017 and 2021 (EUROSTAT⁹⁸)

Country of citizenship	2017		2018		2019		2020		2021	
	Forced return	Voluntary return								
Albania	82	99	219	113	184	261	93	254	60	345
Serbia	289	702	729	518	618	845	425	704	315	840
Türkiye	30	84	140	40	63	199	85	173	55	145
Algeria	138	51	41	95	59	34	7	15	0	10
Egypt	10	25	41	17	15	45	22	39	5	45
Morocco	95	25	23	84	44	21	9	14	5	10
Tunisia	32	19	18	17	21	25	4	11	5	25
Nigeria	199	131	213	272	306	169	96	148	110	160
Afghanistan	118	237	226	180	266	214	49	97	65	75
Bangladesh	2	7	12	17	14	8	1	11	20	15
India	25	69	116	44	45	140	10	91	30	90
Pakistan	61	69	77	74	59	64	27	42	30	40
Iraq	4	685	618	23	2	323	1	98	0	165
Total	1 671	4 442	4 925	2 482	2 584	4 816	1 306	3 688	1 045	3 945

⁹⁷ TCNs who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship:
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_vol_custom_12119736/default/table?lang=en

⁹⁸ TCNs who have left the territory by type of return and citizenship:
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_vol_custom_12119736/default/table?lang=en

Figure 19: Third-country nationals returned to the country of citizenship or an other third-country, following an order to leave, by sex and type of return (EUROSTAT⁹⁹)

Figure 20: Type of return by country of destination: country of citizenship or other third-country (EUROSTAT¹⁰⁰)

⁹⁹ TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex – quarterly data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1_custom_12119851/default/table?lang=en

¹⁰⁰ TCNs returned following an order to leave, by type of return, citizenship, country of destination, age and sex – quarterly data:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirtn1_custom_12119870/default/table?lang=en

Table 13: List of cited experts (expert interviews and workshop participants) including text reference, date, area of expertise, institutional affiliation (expert interviews); date, topics, composition of participants (expert workshops)

Expert interviews		
Reference in the text	Area of expertise	Institutional affiliation
Expert interview 01, 06/2023	Asylum and Immigration Law	Privat law firm
Expert interview 02, 06/2023	Human rights	Governmental institution (provincial level)
Expert interview 03, 06/2023	Integration and diversity management	Governmental institution (provincial level)
Expert interview 04, 06/2023	Legal and social counseling	Third sector organisation
Expert interview 05, 03/2024	Return, Reintegration and Quality Development	Department Return, Reintegration and Quality Development of the Federal Ministry of the Interior
Expert interview 06, 03/2024	Return, Reintegration and Quality Development	Department Return, Reintegration and Quality Development of the Federal Ministry of the Interior
Expert workshop 01, 05/2023	Data on irregular migration in Austria: needs, use and challenges	Researchers, third sector organisations, governmental institutions